

Master thesis

Spectral Analysis of event-based time-series

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Abstract

Many real-world systems are characterised by data that is not given in classical amplitude-time-value pairs. Instead, their dynamics are recorded as discrete events. There are many examples in nature, e.g. cardiac signals and extreme events like volcanic eruptions or wild fires, as well as in the complex anthropogenic world, with examples like stock markets shocks or arrival times of vehicles. The lack of amplitude information, limited number of non-equidistant samples as well as the high levels of noise render these signals difficult to analyse using conventional time series analysis methods. Among the latter, power spectral analysis is arguably among the most powerful and widespread approaches to better understand the underlying mechanisms of continuous time-series. In my master thesis, I propose four novel methods to estimate and analyse the power spectrum of discrete event-based data. Two of these methods are based on the definition of a correlation coefficient and the Wiener-Khinchin Theorem, while the other two are based on the idea of reconstructing a continuous time-series using a series expansion. After defining these methods, I assess their performance on analytic examples and real-world data of the Strokkur Geyser in Iceland. This data records the eruption events of the geyser from the 27th June 2017 till the 10th June 2018. As an illustration of the advantages and disadvantages of the methods and to ensure that the major assumptions of these methods hold, I will focus solely on the events from the 1st December to the 7th December, in this work. As a result of this analysis, I show that the two correlation based methods and one of the series expansion methods are not able to reconstruct the entire power spectrum. Instead, they harvest promising results on subsets of the spectrum. The last series expansion method, however, yields reliable results, which could lead to a better understanding of the geyser's dynamics when analysed further. This thesis, and the four methods derived in it, will help to push the research boundary on the spectral analysis of event-based time-series further.

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1. Introduction

The spectral analysis of signals and data is well established, with a pivotal event being the proposal of the Fourier transform in 1822 by Joseph Fourier [1]. Over the years, these methods have been improved and are widely used in many contexts, from astrophysics [2] to quaternary sciences [3]. These methods, however, focus on the analysis of general time-series, which are given in amplitude and time-value pairs $X_m = (t_i, x_i)_{i \in \{1, \dots, m\}}$ and ordered in the time-domain $t_i < t_{i+1}$. However, many systems are only measurable in a way in which it is impossible to obtain these amplitude and time-value pairs. Instead, these measurements return only the time-values t_i . This kind of data is often called discrete or event-based data [4]. There are many examples of such systems, from the human body, e.g. the discrete heart beats coupling to the continuous rhythm of respiration [5] or the firing of neurons (often modeled as spike-trains) [6], to larger, more complex systems in nature, e.g. geyser's and their activity [7], or complex anthropogenic systems such as fertilizer supply systems and resulting supply shocks [8].

Analysing this kind of data would help in the understanding of the underlying systems and the development of predictive models.

In 2023, Marwan & Braun proposed a new method to generate and analyse spectral information, by estimating the power spectrum density from event-data [4]. Using a metric called the edit-distance, which is able to obtain a distance between one-dimensional objects, such as strings or words [9], they defined a way to calculate a correlation coefficient. This correlation coefficient was then used to calculate an autocorrelation function, whose Fourier transform is an estimation of the power spectrum density [4]. Due to the way this method is defined, the autocorrelation function, however, is always positive, which in turn affects its Fourier transform.

In this master thesis, I want to build on this work and want to propose and investigate four novel methods to obtain and analyse spectral information of event-based data. To achieve this, I will establish the theoretical background in the first section (sec. 2), by defining the mathematical basics (subsec. 2.1), such as the mathematical spaces, which I will use, and their notation. After that, I will establish the spectral analysis for classical, general time-series (subsec. 2.2), before moving on to the event-based time-series (subsec. 2.3) and their basic analysis tools (subsec. 2.4). In the last part of the theoretical background, I will present the above mentioned method by Marwan & Braun in more detail (subsec. 2.5).

With the theoretical background out of the way, I will start to introduce the novel methods in the next section (sec. 3). Therefore, I will begin with the Cosine-Correlation-Measure (subsec. 3.1), define it (subsubsec. 3.1.1), test it on analytic examples (subsubsec. 3.1.3) and investigate how it is used to obtain spectral information and its nuances w.r.t. the autocorrelation function (subsubsec. 3.1.3).

After this, I will move on to the next method, the Overlap-Measure, in the next section (subsec. 3.2). Again, I will start the investigation by defining the method (subsubsec. 3.2.1), then testing it on analytical examples (subsubsec. 3.2.2) and finally establish the way it is used to obtain spectral information (subsubsec. 3.2.3).

In the following subsection, I will establish and investigate the third method. Called the AvIT-Expansion, this method utilises another Ansatz, which will be described in the beginning

(subsec. 3.3), before defining the method itself (subsubsec. 3.3.1). Then I will investigate how this method is able to obtain spectral information (subsubsec. 3.3.2) and test it on some analytical examples (subsubsec. 3.3.3). In the last part of this subsection, I will investigate how alternative ways to define the AvIT-Expansion change its results (subsubsec. 3.3.4). The last subsection will focus on the last method, the LANGE-Expansion (subsec. 3.4). Here I will also start with the analytic definition (subsubsec. 3.4.1), before explaining how spectral information is obtained (subsubsec. 3.4.2). In the last two parts, I will investigate its behaviour w.r.t. analytic examples (subsubsec. 3.4.3) and alternative ways of defining the method (subsubsec. 3.4.4).

In the following section, I will test all four methods on real-world data (sec. 4), in this case the Strokkur geyser in Iceland, with data obtained by the team of Eibl et al. [7].

I will summarize the background of the data and findings of Eibl et al. in the first subsection of this chapter (subsec. 4.1). In the second subsection I will analyse this data, using first the Cosine-Correlation-Measure (subsec. 4.2), then, in the third subsection, the Overlap-Measure (subsec. 4.3, in the fourth, the AvIT-Expansion (subsec. 4.4) and at last the LANGE-Expansion, in the last subsection (subsec. 4.5).

In the end, I will discuss the performance of these methods (sec. 5) and conclude how their advantages and disadvantages are best used and avoided in the analysis of event-based time-series and which aspects of the methods should be further investigated (sec. 6).

2. Theoretical background

In the following section, I introduce the mathematical notations and definitions, which are necessary to discuss the spectral analysis of event-based time-series. Before focussing on this special kind of time-series, I will start by introducing the mathematical basics of the analysis of continuous time-series in the following subsection.

2.1. Mathematical Basics

The classical literature on time-series analysis just focusses on continuous time-series (see [10]) and uses the approach of defining a time-series as a sequence $(x_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ with $x_{n+1} = F(x_n)$ as a discrete representation of $\frac{d}{dt}x(t) = f(t, x(t))$ (see [11]). However, this is not the only approaches to the matter. For a stochastic approach, see [12]. The reason why I chose a different entry into the topic is that the analysis of event-based time-series is impossible with these assumptions of e.g. equally-spaced samples in time, which we will later discuss (see (subsec. 2.3)).

Therefore, let us consider the space of all sequences with values in \mathbb{R} called $\mathcal{S}(\mathbb{R})$. An arbitrary element in this space is the sequence $(u_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$, which contains $|\mathbb{N}|$ elements and can therefore be written as $(u_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} = (u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{n-1}, u_n, u_{n+1}, \dots)$. A sub-space of $\mathcal{S}(\mathbb{R})$ is $\mathcal{S}^<(\mathbb{R}^+)$. An element $(v_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \in \mathcal{S}^<(\mathbb{R}^+)$ has to fulfill two criteria:

$$\forall (v_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \in \mathcal{S}^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \subset \mathcal{S}(\mathbb{R}) : \quad (1)$$

$$1. v_n \in \mathbb{R}^+ \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N} \quad (2)$$

$$2. v_{n-1} < v_n < v_{n+1} \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N}. \quad (3)$$

This space is the space of the sequences on \mathbb{R}^+ , i.e. the positive real numbers, whose elements are sorted in ascending order. While the space $\mathcal{S}(\mathbb{R})$ contains any arbitrary sequence, the intuition behind the sub-space $\mathcal{S}^<(\mathbb{R}^+)$ is that the elements are sequences of time-measurements, which are by nature always positive and ordered.

Now, let us consider the outer sum \oplus . This is defined as:

$$\oplus : \mathcal{S}(\mathbb{R}) \times \mathcal{S}(\mathbb{R}) \rightarrow \mathcal{S}(\mathbb{R}^2) \quad (4)$$

$$((u_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}, (v_k)_{k \in \mathbb{N}}) \mapsto (w_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} = ((u_n), (v_n))_{n \in \mathbb{N}}. \quad (5)$$

So that for an arbitrary element $w_i \in (w_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ follows $w_i = (u_i, v_i)$.

A projection of the space $\mathcal{S}(\mathbb{R})$ is the space $\mathcal{S}_m(\mathbb{R})$ with $m \in \mathbb{N}$. This space is defined as

$$(u_n)_{n \in \{1, \dots, m\}} \in \mathcal{S}_m(\mathbb{R}) \Leftrightarrow |(u_n)_{n \in \{1, \dots, m\}}| = m. \quad (6)$$

With $|\cdot|$ being the cardinality. Meaning that the space $\mathcal{S}_m(\mathbb{R})$ consists of the sequences with length m . It is clear that any map $f : \mathcal{S}(\mathbb{R}) \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_m(\mathbb{R})$ can at best be surjective but can never be bijective.

Such subspaces exist also for $\mathcal{S}^<(\mathbb{R}^+)$ and $\mathcal{S}(\mathbb{R}^2)$, and are called $\mathcal{S}_m^<(\mathbb{R}^+)$ and $\mathcal{S}_m(\mathbb{R}^2)$ respectively.

Any physical measurement M could therefore be mathematically described as

$$M : \mathcal{S}^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \times \mathcal{S}(\mathbb{R}) \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_m^<(\mathbb{R}^+, \mathbb{R}) \quad (7)$$

$$((v_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}, (u_k)_{k \in \mathbb{N}}) \mapsto (v_n)_{n \in \{1, \dots, m\}} \oplus (u_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, m\}} = ((v_n), (u_n))_{n \in \{1, \dots, m\}} = (w_n)_{n \in \{1, \dots, m\}}, \quad (8)$$

$$\text{with } v_{n-1} = w_{n-1}^x < w_n^x < w_{n+1}^x \quad (9)$$

I call any $(w_n)_{n \in \{1, \dots, m\}}$ obtained in such way a **general time-series** X_m . With the intuition that the elements of $X_m = (t_i, x_i)_{i \in \{1, \dots, m\}}$ are pairs of a time-value t_i , recording the time of the measurement, with some sort of physical measurement amplitude x_i . With this in mind, I call the space of these time-series **physical-data space** $\Pi_m := \mathcal{S}_m^<(\mathbb{R}^+, \mathbb{R})$, which is of dimension $2m$. I call any time-series a **simple time-series** χ_m if $\forall i \in \{1, \dots, m-1\}$ $t_{i+1} - t_i = \Delta t = \text{const.}$, i.e. the measurement of the amplitudes x_i are equally-spaced in time.

In the following, I will denote a function f mapping from the set D to W , i.e. $f : D \rightarrow W$, as an element of the **function space** $\mathcal{F}(D, W)$.

2.2. Spectral Analysis of the General Time-Series

Before I can focus on the spectral analysis of a general time-series X_m I have to define other quantities which can be derived from that time-series. The first and most obvious is the **simple mean** of the time-series $\mu(X_m)$. This can be defined as

$$\mu : \Pi_m \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \quad (10)$$

$$(t_i, x_i)_{i \in \{1, \dots, m\}} \mapsto \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m x_i. \quad (11)$$

With the naming convention that $\mu(X_m) = \mu$.

To introduce further concepts, which are well known for functions, one has to think of a coherent way to represent a general time-series as a function, i.e. a transformation $f : \Pi_m \rightarrow \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{R})$. There is no *a priori* right transformation, but I will use a transformation, which uses the step function as basis, centered around the time-stamp t_i of the value x_i and therefore is given by:

$$f : \Pi_m \rightarrow \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{R}) \quad (12)$$

$$(t_i, x_i)_{i \in \{1, \dots, m\}} \mapsto \sum_{i=1}^m x_i \mathbb{1}_{\frac{t_{i+1}+t_i}{2} < t \leq \frac{t_i+t_{i+1}}{2}} + \mathbb{0}. \quad (13)$$

With the definition of the step function being:

$$\mathbb{1}_{x>b} : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [0, 1] \quad (14)$$

$$x \mapsto \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x > b \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases}. \quad (15)$$

And the zero-function $\mathbb{0} = 0 \forall x \in \mathbb{R}$ ensuring that the function is defined for all time-values, by mapping every time-value $t \notin [t_1, t_m]$ to zero. This transformation is only important for the following definitions as the inspiration on how to define the following operations on Π_m from known concepts on $\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{R})$. It is of course easy to understand that a general time-series X_m , with $m \rightarrow \infty$ and $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$, converges to some function $x(t)$, and one can easily see that the same also follows for the transformation $f(X_m)$, s.t.

$$\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0} f(X_m) \rightarrow x(t). \quad (16)$$

With this in mind, one can define another important quantity: the **time-resolved mean** $\gamma(X_m)$, which I defined as:

$$\gamma : \Pi_m \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \quad (17)$$

$$(t_i, x_i)_{i=\{1, \dots, m\}} \mapsto \frac{1}{t_m - t_1} \left(\sum_{i=2}^{m-1} \frac{x_i}{2} (t_{i+1} - t_{i-1}) + x_1(t_2 - t_1) + x_m(t_m - t_{m-1}) \right). \quad (18)$$

With the common definition that for a **simple time-series** $\chi_m \forall i \in \{1, \dots, m-1\} t_{i+1} - t_i = \Delta t = \text{const.}$, the time-resolved mean coincides with the simple mean, i.e. $\mu(\chi_m) = \gamma(\chi_m)$ (see proof here subsec. A.1).

Analogously one can define the **simple standard-deviation** with:

$$\text{std} : \Pi_m \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \quad (19)$$

$$(t_i, x_i)_{i=\{1, \dots, m\}} \mapsto \sqrt{\frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m (x_i - \mu)^2} \quad (20)$$

and the **time-resolved standard-deviation**

$$\text{std}_{\text{time}} : \Pi_m \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \quad (21)$$

$$(t_i, x_i)_{i=\{1, \dots, m\}} \mapsto \sqrt{\frac{1}{t_m - t_1} \sum_{i=2}^{m-1} \frac{(x_i - \gamma)^2}{2} (t_{i+1} - t_{i-1}) + (x_1 - \gamma)^2 (t_2 - t_1) + (x_m - \gamma)^2 (t_m - t_{m-1})}. \quad (22)$$

Here also follows $\text{std}_{\text{time}}(\chi_m) = \text{std}(\chi_m)$, see(subsec. A.2).

Of course, the simple and the time-resolved mean and standard deviation can also be defined on $\mathcal{S}_m(\mathbb{R}^2)$ instead of the sub-space Π_m , but I chose this to emphasize the physical background of the data. Later on, I will use them both on $\mathcal{S}_m(\mathbb{R}^2)$, but I will not bother to write another definition for them on this space since it is analogous.

One can also define a **time-shift operator** $T_{X_m}(\tau)$ as a function of τ

$$T_{X_m}(\tau) : \Pi_m \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \Pi_{j \leq m} \quad (23)$$

$$((t_i, x_i)_{i=\{1, \dots, m\}}, \tau) \mapsto (t_{i+k(i)}, x_{i+k(i)})_{i=\{1, \dots, j\}}, \quad (24)$$

$$\text{with } k(i) = \min_{l=1, \dots, m} l \text{ s.t. } t_i + \tau \leq \frac{t_{i+l} + t_{i+l+1}}{2}, \quad (25)$$

$$\text{and } j = \max_{l=1, \dots, m} l \text{ s.t. } l + k(l) \leq m. \quad (26)$$

Here, every pair of the time-series X_m gets shifted by an individual index $k(i)$, which is the smallest possible index-shift l , for which the time-lagged value, i.e. $t_i + \tau$, is smaller than the upper bound of its the underlying step-function $\frac{t_{i+l} + t_{i+l+1}}{2}$. Since the original time-series X_m has a finite length m , the length of the time-shifted series is determined by the maximal index l which, when shifted by $k(l)$ still maps to a pair of the original time-series X_m . Therefore, it is possible that the time-shift maps a time-series on a lower-dimensional space. From this, it follows that this shift is not bijective and therefore not invertible.

This operator is at first not necessary to define an autocorrelation function for the simple and general case, but it will be necessary later on.

The autocorrelation function, in the continuous case for a \mathbb{C} -valued function $x(t)$, is a function $R(\tau) \in \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{R}, [-1, 1])$ depending on the time-lag τ and usually defined as

$$R(\tau) = \frac{1}{\int |x(t)|^2 dt} \int x(t)x^*(t - \tau) dt. \quad (27)$$

In the case the **simple autocovariance function** can be defined for a simple time-series χ_m with the following map (similar to [10] [12], [11])

$$\rho'_{X_m} : \Pi_m \rightarrow \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{R}) \quad (28)$$

$$(t_i, x_i)_{i=\{1, \dots, m\}} \mapsto \rho'_{X_m}(\tau) = \sum_{i=1}^m (x_i - \mu)(x_{i+k} - \mu) \mathbb{1}_{i+k \leq m} \text{ with } k = \left\lfloor \frac{2\tau}{\Delta t} \right\rfloor. \quad (29)$$

Since the result is a real-function with the argument τ , the map ρ'_{X_m} maps to the space of real functions $\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{R})$. To define an autocovariance function for a general time-series X_m is more difficult, but the idea is the same: one can define this **general autocovariance function** $\rho(\tau)$ with the map

$$\rho_{X_m} : \Pi_m \rightarrow \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{R}) \quad (30)$$

$$(t_i, x_i)_{i=\{1, \dots, m\}} \mapsto \rho_{X_m}(\tau) = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^m (x_i - \gamma)(x_j - \gamma) \mathbb{1}_{\frac{t_{i-1} + t_i}{2} < t_j + \tau \leq \frac{t_i + t_{i+1}}{2}}. \quad (31)$$

The normalized general autocovariance function $\varrho = \frac{\rho(\tau)}{\rho(0)} \in \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{R}, [-1, 1])$ is called **general autocorrelation function** (ACF). The same follows for the **simple autocorrelation function** $\varrho' = \frac{\rho'(\tau)}{\rho'(0)}$. The subtraction of the mean and this normalisation are quite common in the literature (see [10] [12], [11]) and improve the intuitive understanding of the corresponding values. These both are functions with $\varrho : \Pi_m \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [-1, 1]$, i.e. mapping the time-series $X_m \in \Pi_m$ and the time-lag $\tau \in \mathbb{R}$ to values between -1 and 1 . The intuitive meaning of the ACF is that it shows the correlation of a time-series with a time-lagged version of itself.

Its maximum $\varrho(\tau_1) = 1$ means that the original time-series correlates to the maximum with a version of itself, which is time-lagged by τ_1 . Meaning that if the amplitude of X_m increases, then the amplitude after the time τ_1 , so $T_{X_m}(\tau_1)$, increases in the same manner. If the amplitude of X_m decreases, the amplitude of $T_{X_m}(\tau_1)$ will also decrease. The meaning of the minimum $\varrho(\tau_2) = -1$ is analogous, but this time with complete anti-correlation. This

means that if the amplitude of X_m increases, the amplitude of $T_{X_m}(\tau_2)$ will decrease and if the amplitude of X_m decreases, the amplitude of the time-lagged version $T_{X_m}(\tau_2)$ will increase. From this, it is obvious that the function $\rho(\tau)$ stores information on the important time-scales and recurrence-times of the time-series X_m .

This brings us to another well-known concept known as the **Wiener-Khinchin Theorem**. This states that the ACF and the **power spectrum density** (PSD) σ are linked with the Fourier transformation (see [10] [11]). Since, with the definition, the ACF is a function on \mathbb{R} , this theorem can be formally described with (see [10])

$$\sigma(f) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \rho(\tau) e^{2\pi i f \tau} d\tau. \quad (32)$$

In the case of real-world data and therefore a discrete equally sampled $\rho(\tau)$, one has to use a discrete representation of the Fourier transform of course, e.g.:

$$\sigma_k = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{n=1}^N \rho_n e^{2\pi i k n / N}. \quad (33)$$

As we will later see, due to this discreteness, there are multiple possible normalisations (e.g. z-normalisation) to exclude side-effects from the sampling of $\rho(\tau)$.

The power spectrum of a time-series is defined as the squared modulus of the continuous Fourier transform of the time-series ([11]). In the discrete case it is often called periodogram ([10], [11], [12]). If it is normalised, so that the integral is equal to 1, it is called the power-spectrum density (PSD). The Wiener-Khinchin-Theorem is advantageous, since sampling of the ACF and therefore also the sampling of the PSD can be chosen after the measurement, while this is impossible for the data set itself. This is important for resolution in Fourier space in order to avoid leakage from one frequency bin into adjacent ones [11]. Another important reason why one should not just transform the original data is the possible presence of noise, since the Fourier transform of the noise is in the same order of magnitude as that of the signal [11]. Only with further normalisation or the use of the Wiener-Khinchin-Theorem one should try to extract the spectrum from the continuous data. The theorem is also of importance for the event-based time-series, since a simple Fourier transformation is not possible, as will be shown later.

Analysing the obtained spectrum is the essence of spectral analysis. Since the Fourier transform is a linear operation, this is also only a linear analysis of the data. Anyway, it can help to obtain relevant time-scales of the system and even find characteristic frequencies of underlying dynamics.

Before we are able to analyse spectra, however, we have to discuss the process of sampling. In the literature, the **sampling theorem**, typically called Shannon's or Nyquist sampling theorem, is usually explained with the following (see [13], [14]):

Consider an \mathbb{R} -valued function $x(t)$. This function is now sampled by a function $g(t)$, given as a Dirac-spike-train.

$$g(t) = \sum_{j=-\infty}^{\infty} \delta(t - jT). \quad (34)$$

One could also use a rectangular function as the basis for $g(t)$, as in [13], with similar results. So the sampled function $x_a(t)$ is the function obtained by sampling $x(t)$ every T time-units. It resembles the real-world data. This real-world data then has the following form:

$$x_a(t) = x(t)g(t). \quad (35)$$

When this is Fourier transformed, the resulting spectrum S_a is given by

$$S_a(f) = S(f) * \frac{1}{T} \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \delta(f - \frac{k}{T}) = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} S(f - \frac{k}{T}), \quad (36)$$

due to the fact that the Fourier transform of a product is equal to the convolution of the Fourier transforms. This shows that this resulting, sampled spectrum $S_a(f)$ has a new periodicity of $\frac{1}{T}$, due to the Dirac-distribution. If the original spectrum $S(f)$ has a limit-frequency f_g , so that $S(f > f_g) = 0$, the relation of f_g and $\frac{1}{T}$ is important. Since the original spectrum has a width of $2f_g$ (due to the symmetry around 0) and the new spectrum repeats the original spectrum every $\frac{1}{T}$, for no information loss, they should therefore fulfill the following ([13] [14]):

$$\frac{1}{T} \geq 2f_g. \quad (37)$$

This is known as the sampling Theorem and when this holds, the original signal is fully recoverable. Alternatively, it can be said that if every T -th time-units is sampled, the highest possible frequency that can be detected is $\frac{1}{2T}$ [14].

Using rectangular base-functions for the sampling would lead to a sinc-function in the Fourier transformation, but this function has the same periodicity, so that the general argumentation is the same (see [13]).

When working in the frequency space, one has to use the dual version of this theorem. If one samples a spectrum $S_p(f)$ again with Dirac distribution with step-size F , i.e. $S_p(f) = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} S(kF)\delta(f-kF)$, the obtained time-series $x_p(t)$ is then again just $x_p(t) = \frac{1}{F} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} x(t - \frac{n}{F})$, i.e. rescaled and with added periodicity of $\frac{1}{F}$. If the duration of the signal $x(t)$ is smaller than $\frac{1}{F}$, it is possible to recover the original spectrum [13] (the analogous quantity of the duration in frequency space is the width of the spectrum, $2f_g$ and therefore is the dual version consistent with the original sampling theorem (eq. 37)). This becomes important later on (subsubsec. 3.4.1).

2.3. Event-Based Time-Series

The topics discussed above are all well-known basic concepts in the time-series analysis community. Now I transfer these well-known concepts to the field of event-based time-series analysis.

Looking at the definition of a general time-series X_m , one sees that I defined it to be the direct sum of an amplitude sequence $(u_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \in \mathcal{S}(\mathbb{R})$ and a time-stamp sequence $(v_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \in \mathcal{S}^<(\mathbb{R})$. Although I called this time-series general, some physical contexts exist in which this

definition is of no use. Take the simple measurement of the daily appearance of the sunrise. This measurement has no amplitude of any kind. The same applies to the occurrence of volcano-eruptions, wildfires, heavy flooding, heartbeats, pulsar-signals and so forth. Here, it is clear that all these measurements are concerning singular events in time, shear moments which have an infinitesimally small width in time. This is why I call such time-series **event-based time-series** T_m and define it as

$$T_m \in \mathcal{S}_m^<(\mathbb{R}^+). \quad (38)$$

Instead of T_m I will sometimes use $(t_n)_{n \in \{1, \dots, m\}}$ to refer to an event-based time-series. If I mention a specific element of the time-series T_m , e.g. the i -th, I will denote this element with $t_i^{T_m}$.

Mathematically this is identical to the timestamps of a general time-series and one could make the point, that one could define an event-based time-series as a sub-form of the general time-series with a definition reading as $Y_m \in \mathcal{S}_m^<(\mathbb{R}^+, \{1\})$, i.e. a general time-series in which everytime t_i the event occurs, an amplitude $x_i = 1$ is returned, giving the time-series the form $Y_m = (t_i, 1)_{i \in \{1, \dots, m\}}$. But one has to be careful with that, since the fundamental physical background is different. This can be seen e.g. in the definition of the time-resolved mean $\gamma(X_m)$ (eq. 17). Each time-stamp is considered as the middle of a step-function with amplitude x_i . If one treats the event-based time-series the same way, the representation of this time-series is just a function $g(t) : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \{1\}$, i.e. it is 1 over the interval $[t_1, t_m]$. This approach does not yield an adequate representation, since it would suggest that the event started at t_1 and ended at t_m , which is clearly not the case. Apart from this intuitive problem, there are some mathematical pitfalls too. If one were to calculate the overlap of two such time-series to calculate e.g. a correlation-coefficient and both happen to, by coincidence, start and end at the same time, this coefficient would be 1, suggesting that each time an event in the first time-series occurs, in the same instance, an event in the second one also occurs, which is in general not the case.

Even without the representation on \mathbb{R} , one sees that the general autocovariance function $\rho(\tau)$ (eq. 30), due to the fact that $\gamma = 1$, is unavoidably $\rho(\tau) = 0 \forall \tau \in \mathbb{R}$.

Now, one might argue that I have to choose another basis-function for the consideration and definitions, e.g. the Dirac distribution, sometimes defined as

$$\delta(t - t_0) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } |t - t_0| > 0 \\ \infty & \text{if } t - t_0 = 0 \end{cases} . \quad (39)$$

However, this is also not sufficient, since the infinitesimal width of the distribution leads to $\rho(\tau) = 0$ for almost every τ , since the width is so small that there is almost no possible τ in which the time-series would overlap with itself. Also, if one tries to calculate the correlation between two such time-series and they do not align, the result will also be zero, which is not helpful for the analysis.

Another difficulty is the number of events, since in many cases for an event-based time-series T_m , m is small. This is a problem since most time-series analysis leans on the assumption that $m \rightarrow \infty$ [10], [11]. Another common assumption is the equally spaced sampling, which is a problem here.

Therefore, one has to find different methods to work with this kind of data.

2.4. Basic Analysis Tools for Event-Based Time-Series

Before I consider the hard task of spectral analysis, I formally introduce the classics of the analysis of sequences. I will begin with the **mean**:

$$\mu : \mathcal{S}_m(\mathbb{R}) \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \quad (40)$$

$$(u_n)_{n \in \{1, \dots, m\}} \mapsto \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m u_i. \quad (41)$$

Another operation which I will use later on and we already discussed in the general case, is the **standard deviation**:

$$\text{std} : \mathcal{S}_m(\mathbb{R}) \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \quad (42)$$

$$(u_n)_{n \in \{1, \dots, m\}} \mapsto \sqrt{\frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m u_i - \mu}. \quad (43)$$

Since these definitions are so similar to the definition of the classic case (eq. 10, eq. 19), I do not other symbols for them and use the same naming convention when possible, i.e. $\mu(T_m) = \mu$.

With these, I focus now on the more interesting analysis tools for event-based time-series.

2.5. Power Spectrum Density Estimation

In 2023, Marwan & Braun introduced a new method to estimate a power spectrum density from event-data [4].

In their work, Marwan & Braun use a measure from the analysis of sequences, the **edit-distance**. This measure calculates the cost of a transformation from one sequence to another and minimises that. This is done by calculating the cost of the 'shortest' possible transformation between two sequences. Typically, the edit-distance is used to calculate a distance between strings or words [9]. The possible transformation steps are chosen as insertion/deletion of elements or shifting elements in time [4].

A possible definition of such a measure applied to event-data time-series could be written as

$$D : \mathcal{S}_{m_1}^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \times \mathcal{S}_{m_2}^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+ \quad (44)$$

$$(T_{m_1}, \mathcal{T}_{m_2}) \mapsto \min \left[\Lambda_S(m_1 + m_2 - 2|\mathcal{C}|) + \sum_{\alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{C}} \Lambda_0 \|t_\alpha^{T_{m_1}} - t_\beta^{\mathcal{T}_{m_2}}\| \right]. \quad (45)$$

Here Λ_S is the cost parameter for insertion and deleting and Λ_0 for shifting, while $\mathcal{C} \subseteq \mathcal{S}_{m_1}^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \times \mathcal{S}_{m_2}^<(\mathbb{R}^+)$ is the set of events which are shifted and $|\mathcal{C}|$ is the number of elements which are shifted.

The ratio of these cost parameters is important since a too high or too low ratio will lead to a preference for one of the operations, which would yield inadequate results.

Marwan & Braun chose $\Lambda_S = 1$ and adjusted Λ_0 [4]. Within a previous work, they found out that the inverse average time interval between all events is a good choice [15], i.e.

$$\Lambda_0 = \frac{m_1 + m_2}{\max\{t_{m_1}^{T_{m_1}}, t_{m_2}^{T_{m_2}}\} - \min\{t_1^{T_{m_1}}, t_1^{T_{m_2}}\}}. \quad (46)$$

In order to obtain a spectrum for event-based time-series, they use an analogous version of the Wiener-Khinchin (eq. 32).

With the following convention that $(t_i^{T_m} + \tau)_{i \in \{1, \dots, m\}} \equiv T_m + \tau$ (which I will also use from here on), they define an ACF for the time-series T_m with the map [4]

$$R_{T_m}^{\text{edit}} : \mathcal{S}_m^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \rightarrow \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{R}, [0, 1]) \quad (47)$$

$$T_m \mapsto R_{T_m}^{\text{edit}}(\tau) = 1 - \tilde{D}_{\text{edit}}(T_m, T_m + \tau). \quad (48)$$

Here $\tilde{D}_{\text{edit}}(T_m, T_m + \tau)$ is the normalised edit-distance between the time-series T_m and the same time-series with a time-lag τ . The normalisation is achieved by calculating a maximum distance, i.e. the edit-distance of the time-series T_m and an empty sequence. With this $\tilde{D}_{\text{edit}}(T_m, T_m + \tau)$ maps to values in the interval $[0, 1]$ and therefore $R_{T_m}^{\text{edit}}(\tau)$ maps to values between 0 and 1.

In order to use the ACF further, one has to calculate it for every τ possible. Formally this can be described by taking a sequence $(\tau_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, M\}} \in \mathcal{S}_M(\mathbb{R})$, with typically $M \gg m$ and $\tau_k - \tau_{k-1} = \Delta\tau = \text{const}$, and performing the following operation:

$$\mathcal{R}_{T_m}^{\text{edit}} : \mathcal{S}_M(\mathbb{R}) \times \mathcal{S}_m^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_M(\mathbb{R}, [0, 1]) \quad (49)$$

$$((\tau_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, M\}}, T_m) \mapsto (\tau_k, R_{T_m}^{\text{edit}}(\tau_k))_{k \in \{1, \dots, M\}}. \quad (50)$$

To get a real mathematical function one has to achieve $\tau_1 \rightarrow -\infty$ and $\tau_M \rightarrow \infty$, but in any real context usually $\tau_M \gg t_m - t_1$ is enough since $R(\tau) \rightarrow 0$ if $\tau \rightarrow \infty$, simply for the reason that an event in a very distant future should be more influenced by events in the recent past and not in the long gone past.

The corresponding spectrum to the time-series T_m is then obtained by taking Fourier transform of the sequence $\mathcal{R}_{T_m}^{\text{edit}}$, analogous to the Wiener-Khinchin-Theorem, defined by Marwan & Braun by the map: [4]

$$S_{T_m}^{\text{edit}} : \mathcal{S}_M(\mathbb{R}, [0, 1]) \rightarrow \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{R}) \quad (51)$$

$$\mathcal{R}_{T_m}^{\text{edit}} \mapsto S_{T_m}^{\text{edit}}(f) = \sum_{k=1}^M \frac{(\mathcal{R}_{T_m}^{\text{edit}})_k^y - \gamma(\mathcal{R}_{T_m}^{\text{edit}})}{\text{std}_{\text{time}}(\mathcal{R}_{T_m}^{\text{edit}})} e^{-2\pi i f \tau_k}. \quad (52)$$

Here, Marwan & Braun use the z-normalisation with the time-resolved mean γ and standard deviation std_{time} on the space $\mathcal{S}_m(\mathbb{R}^2)$ as previously discussed in (eq. 17, eq. 21). I also use the naming convention I briefly used earlier (see eq. 9) that for $(w_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} = ((u_n), (v_n))_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \in \mathcal{S}(\mathbb{R}^2)$, $w_i^x = u_i$ and $w_i^y = v_i$, so that $(\mathcal{R}_{T_m}^{\text{edit}})_k^y = R_{T_m}^{\text{edit}}(\tau_k)$.

Marwan & Braun then use this to calculate spectra from different physical scenarios, namely

random, periodic, autoregressive and chaotic event time-series. Here, chaotic event time-series are events obtained by taking the local maxima from a continuous chaotic system [4]. While their spectra seem promising, one can see that their Ansatz has some difficulties. One pitfall is imposed by their definition for the ACF (eq. 47) can only possibly lead to a function mapping to the interval $[0, 1]$, since the edit-distance is always positive. This, of course, means that a correlation measure that also captures anti-correlation can not be derived from the ACF. In many real-world applications, it is vital to capture anti-correlations, hence more appropriate methods should be developed.

3. Novel Methods to analyse event-based time-series

In the following section, I present four new methods for the analysis of event-based time-series. Therefore, I will discuss the idea and analytics of each of them in the following four subsections. After that I will investigate their performance on a data set of geyser data. The first two methods will present novel methods to estimate correlations between event-data time-series, while the last two present novel methods using series expansion methods.

3.1. Correlation Estimation using the Cosine-Correlation-Measure

My first approach to the topic is to find a way to define a correlation measure that is able to capture every aspect of the correlation. The following section focuses on one of the two methods I derived.

The first measure I propose is the **Cosine-Correlation-Measure** (CCM). Formally, this is a map which could be defined like this

$$\rho^{\text{CCM}} : \mathcal{S}_m^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \times \mathcal{S}_n^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \rightarrow [-1, 1] \quad (53)$$

$$(T_m, \mathcal{T}_n) \mapsto \rho^{\text{CCM}}(T_m, \mathcal{T}_n). \quad (54)$$

3.1.1. Definition

To have a proper correlation measure, I also demand that the CCM has the following three properties:

$$\rho^{\text{CCM}}(T_m, T_m) = 1, \quad \forall T_m \in \mathcal{S}_m^<(\mathbb{R}^+), \quad (55)$$

$$\rho^{\text{CCM}}(T_m, \mathcal{T}_n) = \rho^{\text{CCM}}(\mathcal{T}_n, T_m), \quad (56)$$

$$\lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \rho^{\text{CCM}}(T_m, T_m + \tau) = 0. \quad (57)$$

i.e. the CCM is maximal for identical time-series, symmetric and essentially zero for time-series with long enough distance in time.

To determine how $\rho^{\text{CCM}}(T_m, \mathcal{T}_n)$ is calculated, I follow the idea that some distance between the elements of the time-series T_m and \mathcal{T}_n is converted into an angle and then the average of the cosine of this angle is taken.

This leads to the following Ansatz:

$$\rho^{\text{CCM}}(T_m, \mathcal{T}_n) = \frac{1}{\mathcal{Z}} \sum_{i=1}^M \cos(\alpha_i). \quad (58)$$

From this, one sees that there are two unknowns to discuss: the normalisation \mathcal{Z} and the angles $(\alpha_l)_{l \in \{1, \dots, M\}}$. I will focus on the angles first. For this, I will make the following Ansatz

$$\alpha_l = \frac{2\pi\vartheta_l}{\Delta\bar{t}}. \quad (59)$$

Here again, there is a normalisation $\Delta\bar{t}$ and some sort of distance ϑ_l . The normalisation is a kind of time-scale coming out of the time-series T_m and \mathcal{T}_n which leads to the CCM reaching

its maximum when $\vartheta_l = \Delta \bar{t} \forall l$. Due to this, I define the "distance" first and then see which time-scale is suitable.

From the Ansätze (eq. 58 eq. 59) follows that the angle, and more importantly the "distance", are not just single value assigned to the time-series pair T_m, \mathcal{T}_n , but are entire sets with cardinality M (we will later see that $M \leq \min\{m, n\}$) and therefore this "distance" has to be obtained in a way element-wise.

To obtain this set, the intuitive idea is very easy: for every element in the time-series T_m , one has to search for the smallest temporal distance to a value from the time-series \mathcal{T}_n . This pairing should be unique and symmetric, so that every value is only paired once.

Therefore one has to define a set $Z_N \subseteq T_m \times \mathcal{T}_n$ (also $Z_N \in \mathcal{S}_N(\mathbb{R}^2)$) whose elements $z_l = (t_i^{T_m}, t_j^{\mathcal{T}_n}) \in Z_N$ fulfill the following conditions:

$$1. |z_l^x - z_l^y| = |t_i^{T_m} - t_j^{\mathcal{T}_n}| \leq |t_k^{T_m} - t_j^{\mathcal{T}_n}| \quad \forall t_k^{T_m} \neq t_i^{T_m} \in T_m \quad (60)$$

$$\wedge |z_l^x - z_l^y| = |t_i^{T_m} - t_j^{\mathcal{T}_n}| \leq |t_i^{T_m} - t_k^{\mathcal{T}_n}| \quad \forall t_k^{\mathcal{T}_n} \neq t_j^{\mathcal{T}_n} \in \mathcal{T}_m \quad (61)$$

$$2. z_{l-1}^y < z_l^y \quad \forall l \in \mathbb{N} \text{ with } 1 < l \leq N \quad (62)$$

$$\wedge z_{l-1}^x < z_l^x \quad \forall l \in \mathbb{N} \text{ with } 1 < l \leq N \quad (63)$$

The first condition (eq. 60, eq. 61) ensures, that a value $t_i^{T_m} \in T_m$ is paired with the value $t_j^{\mathcal{T}_n} \in \mathcal{T}_n$, for which the temporal distance is smallest. This condition is, of course, formulated symmetrically.

The second condition (eq. 62, eq. 63) ensures that these pairings are unique and that if two values are paired to the same value from other time-series, the smaller of these values is chosen.

It is clear that these conditions are totally symmetric and therefore $Z_N \subseteq T_m \times \mathcal{T}_n = Z'_N \subseteq \mathcal{T}_n \times T_m$. It is also clear that a map $f : \mathcal{T}_n \times T_m \rightarrow Z_N$ is in general not injective or surjective. Now one can also see that these conditions actually define a entire set of subsets $(Z_i)_{i \in \{1, \dots, K\}}$ (since it is only need twice, I will use the notation for sequences for the sake of simplicity, eventhough this is a set of sets and not a sequence of values in \mathbb{R}) and for every set $T_m \times \mathcal{T}_n$ there are multiple subsets which fulfill these conditions (namely if you found such a subset Z_N and remove one element, the set $Z_{N-1} \forall N > 1$ also fulfills the conditons eq. 60, eq. 63). However, I am only interested in the subset with the maximal cardinality: $\bar{Z}_K \in (Z_i)_{i \in \{1, \dots, K\}}$, i.e. it fulfills

$$\max_{\forall i \in \{1, \dots, K\}} \{|Z_i|\} = |\bar{Z}_K|. \quad (64)$$

With this subset, I am now able to define the 'distance' ϑ_l :

$$f : \bar{Z}_K \rightarrow \Theta' \in \mathcal{S}_K(\mathbb{R}^+) \quad (65)$$

$$(z_l)_{l \in \{1, \dots, K\}} \mapsto \vartheta'_l = |z_l^x - z_l^y|. \quad (66)$$

The subset Θ' is not the final set from which the angles will be obtained, but this technicality will be discussed later since the time-scale $\Delta \bar{t}$ is important for the formulation of this final set Θ .

Now, with basic form of the angles defined, one has to settle on a time-scale $\Delta\bar{t}$. Here, I define three competing possibilities. The first follows the intuition that the change in the combined system, from which the events-based time-series T_m and \mathcal{T}_n are obtained, follows the smallest of the average inter-event times of the time-series. This leads to the first of the possible definitions for $\Delta\bar{t}$:

$$\Delta\bar{t}_{\text{avg}} : T_m \times \mathcal{T}_n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+ \quad (67)$$

$$((t_i^{T_m})_{i \in \{1, \dots, m\}}, (t_j^{\mathcal{T}_n})_{j \in \{1, \dots, n\}}) \mapsto \min \left\{ \frac{t_m^{T_m} - t_1^{T_m}}{m-1}, \frac{t_n^{\mathcal{T}_n} - t_1^{\mathcal{T}_n}}{n-1} \right\}. \quad (68)$$

In the following, I will use the convention $\Delta\bar{t}_{\text{avg}}(T_m, \mathcal{T}_n) = \Delta\bar{t}_{\text{avg}}$. Since $m-1, n-1$ are the number of inter-event times and $t_m^{T_m} - t_1^{T_m}, t_n^{\mathcal{T}_n} - t_1^{\mathcal{T}_n}$ are just the durations of the time-series, it is clear that the ratios are the desired average inter-event times.

Other possible definitions for the time-scale $\Delta\bar{t}$ include the minimal inter-event time $\Delta\bar{t}_{\text{min}}$ and the maximum inter-event time $\Delta\bar{t}_{\text{max}}$.

Their definitions are:

$$\Delta\bar{t}_{\text{min}} : T_m \times \mathcal{T}_n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+ \quad (69)$$

$$((t_i^{T_m})_{i \in \{1, \dots, m\}}, (t_j^{\mathcal{T}_n})_{j \in \{1, \dots, n\}}) \mapsto \min \left\{ \min_{p \in \{2, \dots, m\}} |t_p^{T_m} - t_{p-1}^{T_m}|, \min_{q \in \{2, \dots, n\}} |t_q^{\mathcal{T}_n} - t_{q-1}^{\mathcal{T}_n}| \right\} \quad (70)$$

and

$$\Delta\bar{t}_{\text{max}} : T_m \times \mathcal{T}_n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+ \quad (71)$$

$$((t_i^{T_m})_{i \in \{1, \dots, m\}}, (t_j^{\mathcal{T}_n})_{j \in \{1, \dots, n\}}) \mapsto \max \left\{ \max_{p \in \{2, \dots, m\}} |t_p^{T_m} - t_{p-1}^{T_m}|, \max_{q \in \{2, \dots, n\}} |t_q^{\mathcal{T}_n} - t_{q-1}^{\mathcal{T}_n}| \right\}. \quad (72)$$

For a simple periodic event-based time-series $\Delta\bar{t}_{\text{avg}} = \Delta\bar{t}_{\text{min}} = \Delta\bar{t}_{\text{max}}$, but in any other case it can be fruitful to prefer one of them over the others, since they have different advantages. We will discuss this further in (subsubsec. 3.1.3)

Other definitions are also possible and might be advantageous for special cases.

When the choice of the time-scale is important, I will mark the choice as a subscript to the correlation coefficient, so that e.g. $\rho_{\text{min}}^{\text{CCM}}$ corresponds with the choice of the time-scale $\Delta\bar{t}_{\text{min}}$. If no subscript is given, the choice of the time-scale has no impact on the matter.

Now, when reminding ourselves of the definition of $\rho^{\text{CCM}}(T_m, \mathcal{T}_n)$ (eq. 58), one can see that the angles α_l (eq. 59) are the only argument of the cosine. And since the cosine is strictly periodic, the last condition (eq. 57), which I wanted the correlation coefficient to fulfill, is not met.

This can be fixed by taking advantage of the fact that for $\vartheta_l = \frac{5}{4}\Delta t$, the angle $\alpha_l = \frac{5\pi}{2}$ and therefore $\cos(\alpha_l) = 0$. So instead of using the angles $\vartheta'_l \in \Theta'$, I have to define one last map:

$$g : \Theta' \in \mathcal{S}_K(\mathbb{R}^+) \rightarrow \Theta \in \mathcal{S}_M(\mathbb{R}^+) \quad (73)$$

$$\vartheta'_l \mapsto \vartheta_l \text{ if } \vartheta'_l \leq \frac{5}{4}\Delta t, \quad (74)$$

with generally $M \leq K$, and use the angles $\vartheta_l \in \Theta$. It is noteworthy that, while Θ' is independent of the choice of the time-scale Δt , this is not the case for the set Θ . Choosing $\Delta t = \Delta \bar{t}_{\max}$, instead of $\Delta t = \Delta \bar{t}_{\text{avg}}$ will in general change the number of possible angles M . A mathematically identical option would be to introduce a Heaviside cutoff

$$\theta(x - x_0) : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [0, 1] \quad (75)$$

$$x \mapsto \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x - x_0 \leq 0 \\ 1 & \text{if } x - x_0 > 0 \end{cases}, \quad (76)$$

into the definition of ρ^{CCM} , but computationally it is advisable to do this step beforehand, to save computational time.

With the last condition of ρ^{CCM} (eq. 57) dealt with and the symmetry condition (eq. 56) also met, since the definition of the angles and time-scales being symmetrically defined (since $|x|, \max\{x, y\}$ and $\min\{x, y\}$ are symmetric), I have to focus on the first condition now (eq. 55).

Right now

$$\rho^{\text{CCM}}(T_m, T_m) = \frac{1}{\mathcal{Z}} \sum_{l=1}^m \cos(0) \quad (77)$$

$$= \frac{m}{\mathcal{Z}}. \quad (78)$$

Coming from the fact that there are m differences $\vartheta_l \in \Theta$ and for all of them follows $\vartheta_l = 0$. Now, to ensure that the first condition (eq. 55) is met, it follows for the normalisation that $\mathcal{Z} = m$. For the general case $\rho^{\text{CCM}}(T_m, \mathcal{T}_n)$ the normalisation is chosen in the following way:

$$\mathcal{Z} = \max\{|T_m|, |\mathcal{T}_n|\} = \max\{m, n\}. \quad (79)$$

i.e. the maximum number of time-steps of the two time-series.

This is again symmetric, leading to a definition of the correlation-coefficient ρ^{CCM} which meets all the conditions I wanted it to fulfill (eq. 55 - eq. 57).

3.1.2. Examples

Before I investigate the ACF obtained with the CCM, I want to form an intuition on how the CCM works as a correlation coefficient between two different event-based time-series.

A benefit of the CCM is that for the simplest cases, the answer is easy to derive analytically. Let, for the first example, T_m and \mathcal{T}_n be two event-based time-series which are strictly periodic with $\Delta t^{T_m} = \Delta t^{\mathcal{T}_n} = \Delta t = \text{const.}$, as already mentioned, in such cases follows $\Delta \bar{t}_{\text{avg}} = \Delta \bar{t}_{\min} = \Delta \bar{t}_{\max} = \Delta t$. The corresponding CCM is therefore

$$\rho^{\text{CCM}} = \frac{1}{\max\{m, n\}} \sum_{i=1}^M \cos\left(\frac{2\pi\vartheta_i}{\Delta t}\right). \quad (80)$$

Now these result depends only on the shifting $\beta \Delta t$ between these events and their number. If in the simplest case $m = n$ and $\beta \in [0, \frac{1}{2}]$, the corresponding CCM would be a function of β , i.e.:

$$\rho^{\text{CCM}} = \cos(2\pi\beta). \quad (81)$$

Therefore at a half-period shift, $\rho^{\text{CCM}} = -1$ and anti-correlation is indicated. If the shift is at a quarter-period, $\rho^{\text{CCM}} = 0$, indicating no correlation. This may seem odd at first, but when considering a corresponding continuous picture, it becomes much clearer, since

$$\int \cos(2\pi x) \cdot \cos\left(2\pi x + \frac{2\pi}{4}\right) dx = \int \cos(2\pi x) \cdot \sin(2\pi x) dx \quad (82)$$

$$= 0. \quad (83)$$

However, the $m = n$ case is really an edge case, therefore let us consider $m > n$. Here, the normalisation $\mathcal{Z} = m$, but the number of unique parings is just n . This leads to the following result for the CCM:

$$\rho^{\text{CCM}} = \frac{n}{m} \cos(2\pi\beta). \quad (84)$$

Let us consider $\beta = 0$. Here, the CCM would then just tell us how likely it is, that an event in time-series T_m is followed by an event in time-series \mathcal{T}_n . The same result is obtained if \mathcal{T}_n had other characteristic time-scales, e.g. with $\Delta t_1^{\mathcal{T}_n} = \Delta t$ and l others: $\Delta t_2^{\mathcal{T}_n} = k_1 \cdot \Delta t$, $\Delta t_3^{\mathcal{T}_n} = k_2 \cdot \Delta t, \dots, \Delta t_{l+1}^{\mathcal{T}_n} = k_l \cdot \Delta t$, with $k_1, \dots, k_l \in \mathbb{N}$, as long as $t_1^{T_m} = t_1^{\mathcal{T}_n}$ and $t_m^{T_m} = t_n^{\mathcal{T}_n}$. A simple example of this case is the correlation between a time-series T_m and a copy of this time-series T_n ($n < m$), which has lost some elements due to e.g. computational errors.

If $\beta \in [0, \frac{1}{2}]$, this likelihood would be weighted by the smallest shifting between the events. Now, in all these cases, I did not consider the case that β is greater than $\frac{1}{2}$, since by definition of ϑ_l as the smallest difference, β is bound by $\frac{1}{2}$. If however the distance between the first values $|t_1^{T_m} - t_1^{\mathcal{T}_n}| > \frac{\Delta t}{2}$ and $t_1^{T_m} < t_1^{\mathcal{T}_n}$, the event $t_1^{\mathcal{T}_n}$ would be paired with the second value of T_m . Even though the first event is neglected for the calculation of the difference, it is still accounted for in the normalisation of the CCM. The same would follow for events whose difference is greater than the cut-off (eq. 74).

If $\Delta t^{T_m} \neq \Delta t^{\mathcal{T}_n}$, there is no easy analytical formula for the CCM. But it can be said that the CCM is periodic (until the cut-off) if and only if $\frac{\Delta t^{T_m}}{\Delta t^{\mathcal{T}_n}} \in \mathbb{Q}$, with frequency $\min\{\Delta t^{T_m}, \Delta t^{\mathcal{T}_n}\}$.

3.1.3. ACF

While obtaining a correlation coefficient for two different event-based time-series is an advantage of the CCM compared to the edit-distance approach, I also want to obtain spectral information from it.

Here, analogous to Marwan & Braun in their study [4], I calculate the CCM between the time-series T_m and a time-lagged version of itself for every desired time-lag τ .

First, one has to define the ACF for a time-series T_m :

$$R_{T_m}^{\text{CCM}} : \mathcal{S}_m^+(\mathbb{R}^+) \rightarrow \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{R}, [-1, 1]) \quad (85)$$

$$T_m \mapsto R_{T_m}^{\text{CCM}}(\tau) = \rho^{\text{CCM}}(T_m, T_m + \tau). \quad (86)$$

Then again, a sequence of these time-lag values is created $(\tau_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, M\}} \in \mathcal{S}_M(\mathbb{R})$, with $\tau_i - \tau_{i-1} = \Delta\tau = \text{const. } \forall i \leq M \in \mathbb{N}$ and is combined with the ACF:

$$\mathcal{R}_{T_m}^{\text{CCM}} : \mathcal{S}_M(\mathbb{R}) \times \mathcal{S}_m^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_M(\mathbb{R}, [-1, 1]) \quad (87)$$

$$((\tau_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, M\}}, T_m) \mapsto (\tau_k, R_{T_m}^{\text{CCM}}(\tau_k))_{k \in \{1, \dots, M\}}. \quad (88)$$

Since the cutoff is analytically defined (eq. 74), the values τ_1 and τ_M can be chosen in such a way that the sequence does not contain any unnecessary zero-values. Therefore one might choose $\tau_1 = t_1^{T_m} - t_m^{T_m} - \frac{5}{4}\Delta t$ and if Δt is not so easy to determine and nothing about the time-series is known, $\tau_1 = \frac{9}{4}(t_1^{T_m} - t_m^{T_m})$ should suffice, since it is the maximum, i.e. the value of the edge-case $M = 2$, which in turn is smallest possible event-based time-series.

Since $\tau_1 = -\tau_M$, the other end is also defined.

Now, following the same procedure as Marwan & Braun, I perform the Fourier transformation

$$S_{T_m}^{\text{CCM}} : \mathcal{S}_M(\mathbb{R}, [-1, 1]) \rightarrow \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{R}) \quad (89)$$

$$\mathcal{R}_{T_m}^{\text{CCM}} \mapsto S_{T_m}^{\text{CCM}}(f) = \sum_{k=1}^M \frac{(\mathcal{R}_{T_m}^{\text{CCM}})_k^y - \gamma(\mathcal{R}_{T_m}^{\text{CCM}})}{\text{std}_{\text{time}}(\mathcal{R}_{T_m}^{\text{CCM}})} e^{-2\pi i f \tau_k}. \quad (90)$$

Now, let us investigate the performance of this on several ideal examples.

The very first is the standard periodic case. Here, the power spectrum estimation (PSE) clearly identifies the present underlying frequency (fig. 1). Now, when investigating the ACF more closely, one can see periodic discontinuities (fig. 2). Although these seem strange, this is a direct consequence of the condition that pairings between events are unique and only between the "closest" ones (eq. 63). This can be best understood by looking at fig. 3. Here, one can see that due to the time-lag of $\tau = -0.51$ only four pairs are allowed in the calculation of the ACF, while the ACF is normalised with all five. This leads to $R_{T_m}^{\text{CCM}} \approx -\frac{4}{5}$ while $\tau \rightarrow -0.5$. But at the moment the time-lag is at $\tau = -0.5$, the number of allowed pairs increases from 4 to 5 and therefore $R_{T_m}^{\text{CCM}} = -\frac{5}{5} = -1$. This leads to a discontinuity. This effect is also seen in fig. 2. Here are the jumps from $-\frac{1}{10}$ to $-\frac{2}{10}$, $-\frac{2}{10}$ to $\frac{3}{10}$ and from $-\frac{4}{10}$ to $\frac{5}{10}$.

Because the discontinuity only occurs when a 'new' pairing is allowed, it follows that, for a periodic event-based time-series with length m , the gap of the discontinuity is $\frac{1}{m}$ wide and therefore when $m \rightarrow \infty$ the gap disappears, since $\frac{1}{m} \rightarrow 0$.

Now, since the general case is not strictly periodic, one should take away from this example that the ACF can have discontinuities, which may seem odd but are due to the way the CCM is defined.

Now, let us investigate another example, to showcase the effect of the different time-scales $\Delta\bar{t}_{\text{avg}}$, $\Delta\bar{t}_{\text{min}}$ and $\Delta\bar{t}_{\text{max}}$.

Figure 1: Left side of the ACF and entire PSE of a simple periodic event-based time-series T_m with $m = 100$, calculated with the Cosine-Correlation-Measure (CCM).

Figure 2: Zoomed in picture of the ACF of a simple periodic event time-series calculated with the CCM. Periodic discontinuities can be seen at $-8.5, -7.5, -6.5$.

Figure 3: Explanatory figure showcasing the underlying dynamics of the discontinuities in the ACF seen in (fig. 2). The red impulses are a representation of the original event-based time-series, while the blue impulses are their time-shifted counterparts. The left graphic shows the pairings at a time-shift of $\tau = -0.51$ a.u. and the right at $\tau = -0.5$ a.u.. The red dashed lines indicate the position of the original events projected onto the time-axis of the time-shifted events. The grey lines between a blue and a dashed red event show a possible pairing which is neglected, due to the conditions of the pairings (eq. 60, eq. 63). The green lines, on the other hand, show the allowed and final pairings. Their respective distance is written under the first of these pairings.

For this, I will define a time-series, which I will call **two-frequency-periodic** (TFP). The TFP is an event-based time-series with two characteristic inter-event times $\Delta t_1, \Delta t_2$. Both are equally present in the signal. The simplest representation of a TFP is a time-series which is defined like this $[0, \Delta t_1, \Delta t_1 + \Delta t_2, 2\Delta t_1 + \Delta t_2, 2(\Delta t_1 + \Delta t_2), 3\Delta t_1 + 2\Delta t_2, \dots]$. The characteristic inter-event times here are not Δt_1 and Δt_2 , instead, they are $\Delta t_1 + \Delta t_2$ and either Δt_1 or Δt_2 . One can see from the example above, that adding $\Delta t_1 + \Delta t_2$ to any element in the time-series leads to another element in the time-series, i.e. it is an inter-event time for every event, while this is not the case for Δt_1 or Δt_2 . For Δt_1 and Δt_2 , only half the events have a corresponding event with this inter-event time, just by definition. Since the knowledge of two of the three time-scales ($\Delta t_1 + \Delta t_2$, Δt_1 or Δt_2) is enough to recover the missing time-scale, recovering two of them means capturing the complete spectral information of the time-series. Therefore I expect to find the frequencies of the pair $(\Delta t_1 + \Delta t_2, \Delta t_1)$ (if $\Delta t_1 < \Delta t_2$) or the pair $(\Delta t_1 + \Delta t_2, \Delta t_2)$ (if $\Delta t_2 < \Delta t_1$) in a spectrum of the TFP.

In this example fig. 4, the time-scales are chosen as $\Delta t_1 = 10$ and $\Delta t_2 = 1$. Therefore, I expect to find the frequency pair $(1, \frac{1}{11})$ in the spectrum. This example of the TFP leads to $\Delta \bar{t}_{\text{avg}} = 5.5$ and therefore, in the spectrum to a peak at $\frac{10}{55}$, since $\frac{10}{55} \approx 0.1818$. Another contribution to this peak could come from a second harmonic of the peak at $0.09'$, which corresponds to $\Delta t = 11$ ($\Delta t_1 + \Delta t_2$), i.e. one of the expected frequencies of the spectrum. Using the $\Delta \bar{t}_{\text{min}}$ time-scale leads to a profound peak at $f = 1$ (see fig. 5) and for $\Delta \bar{t}_{\text{max}}$ the peak is clearly at $f = \frac{1}{11}$ (see fig. 6), corresponding each to one of the two major distances in the time-series.

Figure 4: Example of the ACF and PSE for a TFP with $\Delta t_1 = 10$ and $\Delta t_2 = 1$ using the $\Delta \bar{t}_{\text{avg}}$ time-scale, computed with the Cosine-Correlation-Measure (CCM). The expected frequencies are marked in orange.

Figure 5: Example of the ACF and PSE for a TFP with $\Delta t_1 = 10$ and $\Delta t_2 = 1$ using the $\Delta \bar{t}_{\min}$ time-scale, computed with the Cosine-Correlation-Measure (CCM). The expected frequencies are marked in orange.

Figure 6: Example of the ACF and PSE for a TFP with $\Delta t_1 = 10$ and $\Delta t_2 = 1$ using the $\Delta \bar{t}_{\max}$ time-scale, computed with the Cosine-Correlation-Measure (CCM). The expected frequencies are marked in orange.

While this all comes with no surprises, the shape of the ACF as a 'classical' representation of the event-based time-series is interesting.

From this, one might argue, that an issue of the CCM is its ability to give reliable information on only one of time-scales of the system. Also, the rather intuitive approach, with the allowed pairings, produces mathematical artifacts which may be difficult to work with, like discontinuities.

It is also clear that these issues are now shown in these artificial scenarios, in which they are most prominent. The 'performance' of the CCM with real data will be shown later.

To fix some of these issues, I tried another approach to the matter, which we will explore in the following section.

3.2. Correlation estimation using the Overlap-Measure

The second Ansatz for a correlation measure will work without any further conditions on the used functions or variables and can be calculated directly from the distance matrix and time-series.

Because the idea from the Ansatz comes from the intuition of an overlap of continuous time-series, I call it the **Overlap-Measure** (OM).

3.2.1. Definition

Since I want the OM to be a proper correlation measure, I will demand that the OM fulfill the same properties as the CCM:

$$\rho^{\text{OM}}(T_m, T_m) = 1, \forall T_m \in \mathcal{S}_m^<(\mathbb{R}^+), \quad (91)$$

$$\rho^{\text{OM}}(T_m, \mathcal{T}_n) = \rho^{\text{OM}}(\mathcal{T}_n, T_m), \quad (92)$$

$$\lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \rho^{\text{OM}}(T_m, T_m + \tau) = 0. \quad (93)$$

To discuss the OM, I have to first introduce the following matrix elements, which will be summed later:

$$r_{i,j}^{T_m \mathcal{T}_n} : T_m \times \mathcal{T}_n \rightarrow [-1, 1] \quad (94)$$

$$(t_i^{T_m}, t_j^{\mathcal{T}_n}) \mapsto \left(\cos\left(\frac{2\pi t_i^{T_m}}{\Delta t^{T_m}} - \frac{2\pi t_j^{\mathcal{T}_n}}{\Delta t^{\mathcal{T}_n}}\right) + \cos\left(\frac{2\pi t_i^{T_m}}{\Delta t^{T_m}} + \frac{2\pi t_j^{\mathcal{T}_n}}{\Delta t^{\mathcal{T}_n}}\right) \right) e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{t_i^{T_m}}{\Delta t^{T_m}} - \frac{t_j^{\mathcal{T}_n}}{\Delta t^{\mathcal{T}_n}} \right)^2}. \quad (95)$$

Here, one can directly see two things: first, the similarities to the overlap of continuous functions is evident when thinking of the trigonometric relation that $\cos(x) \cdot \cos(y) \sim \cos(x+y) + \cos(x-y)$ and second, I directly introduced a cutoff-function in this matrix-element. This Gaussian cutoff will later ensure the convergence to zero (eq. 93).

Now, the Ansatz for the correlation coefficient itself is just the sum over these matrix elements with proper normalisation:

$$\rho^{\text{OM}} : \mathcal{S}_m^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \times \mathcal{S}_n^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \rightarrow [-1, 1] \quad (96)$$

$$(T_m, \mathcal{T}_n) \mapsto \frac{1}{\mathcal{Z}} \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n r_{i,j}^{T_m \mathcal{T}_n}. \quad (97)$$

An important difference to the CCM can be seen here directly: the OM is obtained by summing over all possible pairs of the two time-series, so that no pairs are excluded.

The normalisation for the CCM was easy to obtain, since it only considered the distance of the closest neighbours, but since this is not the case for the OM, the normalisation here has no easy expression, since

$$\rho^{\text{OM}}(T_m, T_m) = \frac{1}{\mathcal{Z}} \sum_{i,j=1}^m \left(\cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{\Delta t^{T_m}}(t_i^{T_m} - t_j^{T_m})\right) + \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{\Delta t^{T_m}}(t_i^{T_m} + t_j^{T_m})\right) \right) e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2\pi}{\Delta t^{T_m}}(t_i^{T_m} - t_j^{T_m}) \right)^2} \quad (98)$$

has, for general T_m , no analytical expression. Therefore, one has to settle with the following definition for the normalisation

$$\mathcal{Z} = \max \left\{ \sum_{i,j=1}^m r_{i,j}^{T_m T_m}, \sum_{i,j=1}^n r_{i,j}^{\mathcal{T}_n \mathcal{T}_n} \right\}. \quad (99)$$

Now, with the normalisation defined in this way, the condition (eq. 93) is met. The symmetry condition is also met with the way I defined the OM, due to the fact that only symmetric functions are used.

With all the conditions met, I have to address the last unknowns in the definition, which are the time-scales Δt^{T_m} , $\Delta t^{\mathcal{T}_n}$. These can be defined in a similar way as the time-scale Δt from the CCM. First, there is the average inter-event time

$$\Delta t_{\text{avg}}^{T_m} : T_m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+ \quad (100)$$

$$(t_i^{T_m})_{i \in \{1, \dots, m\}} \mapsto \frac{t_m^{T_m} - t_1^{T_m}}{m - 1}. \quad (101)$$

Secondly, there is the smallest inter-event time of the time-series

$$\Delta t_{\text{min}}^{T_m} : T_m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+ \quad (102)$$

$$(t_i^{T_m})_{i \in \{1, \dots, m\}} \mapsto \min_{p \in \{2, \dots, m\}} |t_p^{T_m} - t_{p-1}^{T_m}|. \quad (103)$$

The last is the maximal inter-event time

$$\Delta t_{\text{max}}^{T_m} : T_m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+ \quad (104)$$

$$(t_i^{T_m})_{i \in \{1, \dots, m\}} \mapsto \max_{p \in \{2, \dots, m\}} |t_p^{T_m} - t_{p-1}^{T_m}|. \quad (105)$$

Although these seem similar to the definitions of the time-scales for the CCM (eq. 67-eq. 71) and, without a doubt, they follow the same intuition, they have different roles in their respective correlation measures. While the time-scale of the CCM is responsible for the periodicity of the entire measure, the time-scales in the OM are better understood as weights to the periodicity of the measure. This comes from the fact that the periodicity of the cosine functions is determined by the product $\Delta t^{T_m} \Delta t^{\mathcal{T}_n}$. Due to that, it is also clear that the OM is not just a more complete or 'better' version of the CCM, but instead they are expected to lead to different results for general data. Therefore, any similarities in the results are not due to similar definitions, but intrinsic properties of the time-series.

But while this is expected for real data, let us investigate some idealistic cases first, for which similar results between the CCM and the OM should be obtained.

3.2.2. Examples

The first example I will consider, is the same simple example which I already used in the analysis of the CCM: the simple periodic time-series T_m , \mathcal{T}_m with $\Delta t^{T_m} = \Delta t^{\mathcal{T}_n} = \Delta t =$

const.

For this, the OM looks at first glance like this:

$$\rho^{\text{OM}} = \frac{1}{\mathcal{Z}} \sum_{k=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n \left(\cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{\Delta t}(t_k^{T_m} - t_j^{\mathcal{T}_n})\right) + \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{\Delta t}(t_k^{T_m} + t_j^{\mathcal{T}_n})\right) \right) e^{\frac{-1}{2\Delta t^2}(t_k^{T_m} - t_j^{\mathcal{T}_n})^2}. \quad (106)$$

I will split the following calculation into three parts. First, I will focus on the cosine functions, second on the normalisation \mathcal{Z} and lastly on the Gaussian cut-off.

Since the starting time $t_1^{T_m} = \Delta t + t'$ is mathematically irrelevant and can be expressed by the time $t_1^{\mathcal{T}_n}$, I will only use the second one, with the convention that $t + \Delta t = t_1^{\mathcal{T}_n}$, therefore the time-series is $T_m = \{\Delta t, 2\Delta t, 3\Delta t, \dots, m\Delta t\}$ and $\mathcal{T}_n = \{\Delta t + t, 2\Delta t + t, 3\Delta t + t, \dots, n\Delta t + t\}$. Now I start with the cosine-terms with the convention above. These simplify to

$$\cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{\Delta t}(k\Delta t \pm j\Delta t \pm t)\right) = \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{\Delta t}(\Delta t(k \pm j) \pm t)\right) \quad (107)$$

$$= \cos\left(2\pi(k \pm j) \pm \frac{2\pi t}{\Delta t}\right). \quad (108)$$

Now, since $i, j \in \mathbb{N} \Rightarrow i \pm j \in \mathbb{Z}$ and since the cosine is symmetric, it follows for the cosine terms

$$\cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{\Delta t}(t_k^{T_m} - t_j^{\mathcal{T}_n})\right) + \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{\Delta t}(t_k^{T_m} + t_j^{\mathcal{T}_n})\right) = 2 \cos\left(\frac{2\pi t}{\Delta t}\right). \quad (109)$$

The OM now simplifies to:

$$\rho^{\text{OM}} = \frac{2 \cos\left(\frac{2\pi t}{\Delta t}\right)}{\mathcal{Z}} \sum_{k=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n e^{\frac{-1}{2\Delta t^2}(t_k^{T_m} - t_j^{\mathcal{T}_n})^2}. \quad (110)$$

I focus now on the double-sum with the cut-off function. I will simplify this term and write it out as an $n \times m$ matrix to simplify it further:

$$\sum_{k=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n \exp\left(\frac{-1}{2\Delta t^2}(t_k^{T_m} - t_j^{\mathcal{T}_n})^2\right) = \sum_{k=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n \exp\left(\frac{-1}{2\Delta t^2}(k\Delta t - j\Delta t - t)^2\right) \quad (111)$$

$$= \sum_{k=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n \exp\left(\frac{-1}{2\Delta t^2}(\Delta t(k - j) - t)^2\right) \quad (112)$$

$$= \exp\left(\frac{-t^2}{2\Delta t^2}\right) \sum_{k=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n \exp\left(\frac{-(k-j)^2}{2\Delta t^2}\right) \exp\left(\frac{(k-j)t}{\Delta t}\right). \quad (113)$$

Now I focus on the terms remaining in the sum and write the elements of this sum out as an $n \times m$ matrix:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & \exp\left(\frac{-1}{2} - \frac{t}{\Delta t}\right) & \exp\left(\frac{-4}{2} - \frac{2t}{\Delta t}\right) & \dots & \exp\left(\frac{-(n-1)^2}{2} - \frac{(n-1)t}{\Delta t}\right) \\ \exp\left(\frac{-1}{2} + \frac{t}{\Delta t}\right) & 1 & \exp\left(\frac{-1}{2} - \frac{t}{\Delta t}\right) & \dots & \exp\left(\frac{-(n-2)^2}{2} - \frac{(n-2)t}{\Delta t}\right) \\ \exp\left(\frac{-4}{2} + \frac{2t}{\Delta t}\right) & \exp\left(\frac{-1}{2} + \frac{t}{\Delta t}\right) & 1 & \dots & \exp\left(\frac{-(n-3)^2}{2} - \frac{(n-3)t}{\Delta t}\right) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \exp\left(\frac{-(m-1)^2}{2} + \frac{(m-1)t}{\Delta t}\right) & \exp\left(\frac{-(m-2)^2}{2} + \frac{(m-2)t}{\Delta t}\right) & \dots & \dots & \exp\left(\frac{-(n-m)^2}{2} - \frac{(n-m)t}{\Delta t}\right) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (114)$$

This matrix is only symmetric if $m = n$. Now, with this representation, one can clearly see that the double sum over all these elements can be written as

$$\min\{n, m\} + \sum_{k=1}^n (n-k) \exp\left(\frac{-k^2}{2} - \frac{kt}{\Delta t}\right) + \sum_{j=1}^m (m-j) \exp\left(\frac{-j^2}{2} + \frac{jt}{\Delta t}\right). \quad (115)$$

Combining this with everything else, one obtains the following so far:

$$\rho^{\text{OM}} = \frac{2 \cos\left(\frac{2\pi t}{\Delta t}\right)}{\mathcal{Z}} e^{\frac{-t^2}{2\Delta t^2}} \left(\min\{n, m\} + \sum_{k=1}^n (n-k) e^{\frac{-k^2}{2} - \frac{kt}{\Delta t}} + \sum_{j=1}^m (m-j) e^{\frac{-j^2}{2} + \frac{jt}{\Delta t}} \right). \quad (116)$$

With this knowledge is the calculation of the normalisation an easy exercise. Since eq. 99 says that the normalisation is determined by the maximum sum over the matrix-elements $r_{k,j}^{T_m T_m}$ and $r_{k,j}^{\mathcal{T}_n \mathcal{T}_n}$ (eq. 94), I shall calculate both to determine the maximum. I will start with $\sum_{k,j}^m r_{k,j}^{T_m T_m}$ and use the fact that here again $i \pm j \in \mathbb{Z}$ and the cosine-terms immediately simplify.

$$\sum_{k,j=1}^m r_{k,j}^{T_m T_m} = 2 \sum_{k,j=1}^m \exp\left(\frac{-1}{2\Delta t^2} (k\Delta t - j\Delta t)^2\right) \quad (117)$$

$$= 2 \sum_{k,j=1}^m \exp\left(\frac{-1}{2\Delta t} (k-j)^2\right). \quad (118)$$

When writing down this double-sum in the same matrix format as above, one directly sees that

$$2 \sum_{k,j=1}^m \exp\left(\frac{-1}{2\Delta t} (k-j)^2\right) = 2 \left(m + 2 \sum_{l=1}^m (m-l) e^{-\frac{l^2}{2}} \right). \quad (119)$$

Now, for $\sum_{k,j}^m r_{k,j}^{\mathcal{T}_n \mathcal{T}_n}$, the difference lies in the cosine terms. Due to the fact that the offset of the values only vanishes in the difference and not in the sum, the sum over the matrix

elements is

$$\sum_{k,j=1}^n r_{k,j}^{\mathcal{S}_n, \mathcal{S}_n} = \left(1 + \cos\left(\frac{4\pi t}{\Delta t}\right)\right) \sum_{k,j=1}^n \exp\left(\frac{-(k-j)^2}{2\Delta t}\right) \quad (120)$$

$$= \left(1 + \cos\left(\frac{4\pi t}{\Delta t}\right)\right) \left(n + 2 \sum_{l=1}^n (n-l)e^{-\frac{l^2}{2}}\right). \quad (121)$$

If $m \geq n$, it is clear that the expression in eq. 119 is greater than or equal to the expression in eq. 121 and therefore the valid choice for the normalisation. If $n > m$ however, this depends heavily on the offset t .

I decide that $m > n$, to show the final result for the OM.

$$\rho^{\text{OM}} = \frac{\cos\left(\frac{2\pi t}{\Delta t}\right) e^{-\frac{t^2}{2\Delta t^2}}}{m + 2 \sum_{l=1}^m (m-l)e^{-\frac{l^2}{2}}} \left(n + \sum_{k=1}^n (n-k)e^{-\frac{k^2}{2} - \frac{kt}{\Delta t}} + \sum_{j=1}^m (m-j)e^{-\frac{j^2}{2} + \frac{jt}{\Delta t}} \right). \quad (122)$$

Like with the CCM, one can see that sign of this expression is solely dependent on the shift between the elements t , i.e. the result of $\cos\left(\frac{2\pi t}{\Delta t}\right)$, since any other term in this result is positive.

When focusing on the essential, one can see that the OM is an overlap of a periodic function with the cut-off function and both of them depend on the offset t and the time-scale Δt .

Even though the OM is not so easy to calculate intuitively compared to the CCM, it is much easier computationally to implement. In the following section, we will explore other advantages when discussing the ACF generated with the help of the OM.

3.2.3. ACF

In order to obtain an ACF and a spectrum, I have to make the same definitions as with the CCM, beginning with defining a map to the ACF as a function of the time-lag τ

$$R_{T_m}^{\text{OM}} : \mathcal{S}_m^+(\mathbb{R}^+) \rightarrow \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{R}, [-1, 1]) \quad (123)$$

$$T_m \mapsto R_{T_m}^{\text{OM}}(\tau) = \rho^{\text{OM}}(T_m, T_m + \tau), \quad (124)$$

with which the complete ACF is defined:

$$\mathcal{R}_{T_m}^{\text{OM}} : \mathcal{S}_M(\mathbb{R}) \times \mathcal{S}_m^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_M(\mathbb{R}, [-1, 1]) \quad (125)$$

$$((\tau_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, M\}}, T_m) \mapsto (\tau_k, R_{T_m}^{\text{OM}}(\tau_k))_{k \in \{1, \dots, M\}}. \quad (126)$$

At last, I define the spectrum:

$$S_{T_m}^{\text{OM}} : \mathcal{S}_M(\mathbb{R}, [-1, 1]) \rightarrow \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{R}\mathbb{R}) \quad (127)$$

$$\mathcal{R}_{T_m}^{\text{OM}} \mapsto S_{T_m}^{\text{OM}}(f) = \sum_{k=1}^M \frac{(\mathcal{R}_{T_m}^{\text{OM}})_k^y - \gamma(\mathcal{R}_{T_m}^{\text{OM}})}{\text{std}_{\text{time}}(\mathcal{R}_{T_m}^{\text{OM}})} e^{-2\pi i f \tau_k}. \quad (128)$$

Figure 7: Left side of the ACF and entire PSE of a simple periodic event-based time-series T_m with $m = 100$, calculated with the Overlap-Correlation-Measure (OM).

The difference to the CCM is in the choice of the length M of the time-lag sequence $(\tau_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, M\}}$ and therefore its starting and ending values τ_1 and τ_M , since the hard cut-off is no longer present. Due to the choice of a Gaussian cut-off will the values of the ACF never be zero analytically, but one has to decide individually on a threshold c after which the values are negligible. Since $c = e^{\frac{-t_0^2}{2\Delta t^2}} \Leftrightarrow t_0 = \sqrt{2 \ln(\frac{1}{c})} \Delta t$ the choice of the time-lag τ_1 is clear: $\tau_1 = t_1^{T_m} - t_m^{T_m} - t_0$.

I will once again start with the simple periodic example. Here, I use the analytic result from the previous section (eq. 122) and for the case of $n = m$ with the offset being $\tau = t$, it follows that $\rho^{\text{OM}} = R_{T_m}^{\text{OM}}(t)$ and one obtains to the following result:

$$R_{T_m}^{\text{OM}}(\tau) = \frac{\cos\left(\frac{2\pi\tau}{\Delta t}\right) e^{\frac{-\tau^2}{2\Delta t^2}}}{m + 2 \sum_{l=1}^m (m-l) e^{-\frac{l^2}{2}}} \left(m + 2 \sum_{k=1}^m (m-k) e^{-\frac{k^2}{2}} \cosh\left(\frac{k\tau}{\Delta t}\right) \right). \quad (129)$$

The hyperbolic cosine here might seem undesirable at first, but for small τ (compared to Δt) it is just one and for large τ or k it is negligible in the product with the respective Gaussian cutoff functions. So one can focus on the essential information of this equation

$$R_{T_m}^{\text{OM}}(\tau) \sim \cos\left(\frac{2\pi\tau}{\Delta t}\right) e^{\frac{-\tau^2}{2\Delta t^2}}. \quad (130)$$

This is also exactly what is shown in the plot of fig. 7. Although this looks like the CCM (fig. 1) it is clear that this graph is a smooth function of τ .

To explore the effect of the different time-scales on this measure, I again consider a TFP. For this case, one can see the first significant performance difference between the CCM and

Figure 8: Example of the ACF and PSE for a TFP with $\Delta t_1 = 10$ and $\Delta t_2 = 1$ using the $\Delta \bar{t}_{avg}$ time-scale computed with the Overlap-Measure (OM). The expected frequencies are marked in orange.

Figure 9: Example of the ACF and PSE for a TFP with $\Delta t_1 = 10$ and $\Delta t_2 = 1$ using the $\Delta \bar{t}_{\min}$ time-scale, computed with the Overlap-Correlation-Measure (OM). The expected frequencies are marked in orange.

the OM (fig. 8) When focusing on the spectra first, one notices that in the spectrum of the OM only the average frequency $f_{\text{avg}} = \frac{10}{55}$ corresponding to the time-scale $\Delta \bar{t}_{\text{avg}} = 5.5$ is recovered. The ACF is also very different, looking more or less like the simple periodic case. When investigating the smaller time-scale $\Delta \bar{t}_{\min}$, the results (fig. 8) of the CCM and the OM look quite similar in the case of the ACF. The results for the spectra show again that the OM recovers mostly one frequency, corresponding to $\Delta \bar{t}_{\min}$, while the spectrum computed with the CCM shows more frequencies. However, apart from the other two cases, side frequencies at positions 1.09, 1.18 and 1.27, i.e. with $\Delta f = 0.09$ (symmetrically around 1.0) are recovered, which can be interpreted as higher order harmonics of the Δt_{\max} frequency. It can not be interpreted as an interaction with the cut-off, since the Gaussian cut-off just leads to a broadening in the peaks of the spectrum (see proof here (subsec. A.3)). In this case follows again, although it is not fully recovered in the spectrum, that the ACF shows an interaction of the two time-scales and is an intuitive representation of the TFP case, with one peak being followed quickly by another peak, with a large pause in between these peak bundles.

When using the time-scale Δt_{\max} instead (fig. 10), the spectrum only recovers the frequency given by its time-scale. Even in the ACF, the other timescale seems to have little effect on the results.

When thinking about the way I defined the OM, one can say that I choose to represent

Figure 10: Example of the ACF and PSE for a TFP with $\Delta t_1 = 10$ and $\Delta t_2 = 1$ using the $\Delta \tilde{t}_{\max}$ time-scale, computed with the Overlap-Correlation-Measure (OM). The expected frequencies are marked in orange.

the event-time-series just by one frequency, even though it can have multiple *a priori*. With this picture in mind, it is clear why it mostly recovered just one frequency in the TFP case. However, since I focused on the ACF and the resulting spectra, the proposed methods (OM and CCM) have potential when used as correlation measures for event-based time-series of the same or different length.

But since the CCM and the OM have these issues w.r.t. the spectral analysis of event-based time-series and since these are not easily fixable, I will examine another Ansatz. The main issue is that one has to define a timescale for the measures, while one is in the search for these time-scales in the signal. This self-referential problem will be addressed in the following two sections, in which I will explore other approaches to this topic.

3.3. Approximation of Continuous Representations using the Average Inter-Event Time-Expansion

In this third approach to the topic, I will use another approach. Instead of *ad hoc* defining a correlation measure, I want to find a way to reconstruct a continuous time-series from the given event data.

This process could be defined mathematically as a map F to the space of functions on \mathbb{R} , $\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{R})$.

$$F : \mathcal{S}_m^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \rightarrow \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{R}) \quad (131)$$

$$T_m \mapsto F(T_m). \quad (132)$$

Although this is a valid way of setting up the following two chapters, I focus more on the perspective of a data scientist. So, instead of just mapping to the space of functions $\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{R})$, I will also map to the physical data space $\Pi_n = S_n^<(\mathbb{R}^+, \mathbb{R})$, which I introduced in the beginning. This way, the methods defined to discuss a general time-series $X_n \in \Pi_n$ can be used. Formally, this mapping therefore may be:

$$F : \mathcal{S}_m^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \rightarrow \Pi_n \quad (133)$$

$$T_m \mapsto F(T_m) = (t_i, x_i)_{i \in \{1, \dots, n\}}. \quad (134)$$

Note that *a priori* there is no connection between n and m . In fact, it makes much more sense for n to be a free parameter, whose choice depends on the physical background of the data. And although one could try to work with expansions defined in this way (eq. 133), my expansions are more concerned with obtaining the amplitudes $(x_i)_{i \in \{1, \dots, n\}}$ of the continuous representation and the set of time-values $(t_i)_{i \in \{1, \dots, n\}}$ is somewhat arbitrary and has to be defined first.

With a given set of time-values $(t_i)_{i \in \{1, \dots, n\}} \in \mathcal{S}_n^<(\mathbb{R}^+)$, my general Ansatz for the mapping for both approaches is:

$$F : \mathcal{S}_n^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \times \mathcal{S}_m^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \rightarrow \Pi_n \quad (135)$$

$$((t_i)_{i \in \{1, \dots, n\}}, T_m) \mapsto F(T_m) = (t_i, x_i)_{i \in \{1, \dots, n\}}. \quad (136)$$

Both maps I propose can be understood with the classical picture of series expansions, in which the event-based time-series are expanded in orders of some timescales Δt_k . The first map will be called **Average Inter-Event Time-Expansion** (AvIT-Expansion).

3.3.1. Definition

As stated above, the AvIT-Expansion is an expansion of an event-based time-series T_m in orders of a set of time-scales $(\Delta t_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, m-1\}} \in \mathcal{S}_{m-1}^<(\mathbb{R}^+)$. I will explain the nuances of this when covering the exact definition of the time-scales. For this expansion to function properly, one also need a set of expansion-coefficients $(a_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, m-1\}} \in \mathcal{S}_{m-1}(\mathbb{R})$ and a set of time-stamps $(t_i)_{i \in \{1, \dots, n\}} \in \mathcal{S}_n^<(\mathbb{R}^+)$. As discussed earlier, these time-stamps and the length of their set n are a free choice of the user, although it makes sense to keep this set equally

sampled, i.e. $t_{i+1} - t_i = \text{const. } \forall i < n \in \mathbb{N}$.

With these ingredients, I define the AvIT-Expansion as follows

$$\mathcal{A}_m : \mathcal{S}_n^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \times \mathcal{S}_m^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \rightarrow \Pi_n \quad (137)$$

$$((t_i)_{i \in \{1, \dots, n\}}, T_m) \mapsto \mathcal{A}_m(T_m) = (t_i, \alpha_{T_m}(t_i))_{i \in \{1, \dots, n\}}, \quad (138)$$

with a real function $\alpha_{T_m}(t)$ defined by the following map:

$$\alpha_{T_m} : \mathcal{S}_m^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \rightarrow \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{R}) \quad (139)$$

$$T_m \mapsto \alpha_{T_m}(t) = \sum_{k=1}^{m-1} a_k \cos\left(\frac{2\pi(t - t_1)}{\Delta t_k}\right). \quad (140)$$

Here, $t - t_1$ is the natural offset of the series, so that it starts at the beginning of the event-based time-series T_m . Of course, one could always transform the time-series to $t_1 = 0$, leaving it meaningless in (eq. 139), but I included it anyway for completeness. In the following analytical examples, the offset is irrelevant, so I will not discuss it any further.

The exciting part about these definitions is the timescales Δt_k and the expansion coefficients a_k . I will start by discussing the timescales first.

I define this as a map Δt_{T_m} , but since I will use this definition only in the context of the AvIT-Expansion, I will drop the subscript later, since it is clear from which time-series these timescales were obtained. I will do the same for the expansion coefficients. The definition of the time-scales in the context of the AvIT-Expansion is:

$$\Delta t_{T_m} : \mathcal{S}_m^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_{m-1}^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \quad (141)$$

$$T_m \mapsto (\Delta t_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, m-1\}} = \left(k \frac{t_m - t_1}{m-1} \right)_{k \in \{1, \dots, m-1\}}. \quad (142)$$

The intuition behind this is simple. The first element Δt_1 is just the duration of the time-series divided by the number of events, which are being followed by another event, so Δt_1 is just the average inter-event time. The second element Δt_2 is just twice this time, so $\Delta t_2 = 2\Delta t_1$, i.e. the average inter-event time, if one event is skipped. So any timescale $\Delta t_k = k\Delta t_1$ describes the average inter-event time between two elements, if $k-1$ other elements are skipped in between. Therefore, it is clear that the last element of this sequence $\Delta t_{m-1} = t_m - t_1$ is just the duration of the time-series. It is clear that these timescales are all positive and increasing, explaining why the map Δt_{T_m} maps to a series whose elements are ordered and positive.

The task of the expansion coefficients a_k is to determine how well a harmonic with a time-scale Δt_k fits to the data given by the event-based time-series. Therefore, the definition of the entire set $(a_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, m-1\}}$ is as follows:

$$\alpha_{T_m} : \mathcal{S}_m^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \times \mathcal{S}_{m-1}^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_{m-1}([-1, 1]) \quad (143)$$

$$(T_m, (\Delta t_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, m-1\}}) \mapsto (a_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, m-1\}} = \left(\frac{1}{m^2} \sum_{i,j=1}^m \cos\left(\frac{2\pi(t_i - t_j)}{\Delta t_k}\right) \right)_{k \in \{1, \dots, m-1\}}. \quad (144)$$

Here, for every coefficient a_k , the distance of every pair of elements $t_i, t_j \in T_m$ is put into a cosine with the respective time-scale Δt_k . If their distance is just a multiple of Δt_k , i.e. $t_i - t_j = n \cdot \Delta t_k$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$, the cosine will be maximal, i.e. showing that this pair is perfectly represented by a harmonic with time-scale Δt_k . The normalisation of the coefficients is also clear. Due to the fact that the cosine is bound by 1, it follows for a time-series T_m with m elements, that there are m^2 pairs whose result is maximal 1. Therefore, $\frac{1}{m^2}$ is chosen as the normalisation. Due to this normalisation, the coefficients are bound by -1 and 1.

The AvIT-Expansion in the representation as a sequence is then just obtained by adding all these time-scales with their respective harmonics together over a suitable time domain, given by $(t_i)_{i \in \{1, \dots, n\}}$.

Now, in order to examine examples, I will present how spectral analysis with the AvIT-Expansion can be done, in the following part.

3.3.2. Spectral Analysis

Since the coefficient a_k is defined using the time-scale Δt_k , the set $(a_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, m-1\}}$ contains the entire spectral information of the AvIT-Expansion and the intuitive meaning of a coefficient $|a_k| \approx 1$ is that occurrence of pairs of the time-series are on average explainable by a underlying process which skips $k - 1$ events. This may be a tool to find hidden frequencies in complex systems. Coefficients with $|a_k| \rightarrow 0$ show that such processes do not play any significant role.

For the spectral analysis, one could follow the standard recipe of calculating the ACF and Fourier transforming the result. But since the idea of a spectrum is to find the characteristic frequencies of a process, one can just plot the set $(|a_k|)_{k \in \{1, \dots, m-1\}}$ over the inverse of the timescales $(\frac{1}{\Delta t_k})_{k \in \{1, \dots, m-1\}}$.

In order to understand the time-scales better, I will focus on a simple example of a timeseries with four events with unit-time-length, i.e. $T_4 = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$ the normalisation of the first-order is $m - 1 = 4 - 1 = 3$, corresponding to the 3 inter-event-times between the pairs (1, 2), (2, 3), (3, 4). Due to the fact that $t_4 - t_1 = 4 - 1 = 3$, the mean time between events is just $\Delta t_1 = 1$. The normalisation of the second-order timescale is the same and therefore the second-order timescale is just $\Delta t_2 = 2$. This corresponds to the time between two elements if one element in between is skipped and therefore with the pairs (1, 3), (2, 4). The next timescale is the one in which 2 elements are skipped, corresponding to the pair (1, 4), with the timescale $\Delta t_3 = 3$. It is clear that the calculation of possible time-scales has to stop now, since there are no other events left to be skipped.

Now, let us investigate the coefficients a_k and therefore use the more general example of a simple periodic time-series $T_m = \{\Delta t, 2\Delta t, 3\Delta t, \dots, m\Delta t\}$. Let us first evaluate the

coefficient of the first-order a_1 , corresponding to the time-scale $\Delta t_1 = \Delta t$:

$$a_1 = \frac{1}{m^2} \sum_{i,j=1}^m \cos\left(\frac{2\pi(i\Delta t - j\Delta t)}{\Delta t}\right) \quad (145)$$

$$= \frac{1}{m^2} \sum_{i,j=1}^m \cos(2\pi(i-j)) \quad (146)$$

$$= \frac{1}{m^2} \sum_{i,j=1}^m 1 = \frac{m^2}{m^2} = 1. \quad (147)$$

For the second order, the timescale is just twice the previous one, i.e. $\Delta t_2 = 2\Delta t$, it follows

$$a_2 = \frac{1}{m^2} \sum_{i,j=1}^m \cos\left(\frac{2\pi(i-j)}{2}\right). \quad (148)$$

This simplifies to

$$a_2 = \frac{1}{m^2} \sum_{i,j=1}^m (-1)^{i-j}. \quad (149)$$

The result of this sum depends on m , if m is even, it follows that this sum vanishes and if it is odd, the sum is 1. I will choose m to be odd and therefore follows for the second coefficient:

$$a_2 = \frac{1}{m^2}. \quad (150)$$

Which is, of course, negligible for large m . When investigating the third-order, a similar picture occurs:

$$a_3 = \frac{1}{m^2} \sum_{i,j=1}^m \cos\left(\frac{2\pi(i-j)}{3}\right). \quad (151)$$

Here again, one has to make assumptions about m . If I e.g. assume that $\exists n \in \mathbb{N}$ s.t. $m = 3n + 1$, this analogously leads to

$$a_3 = \frac{1}{m^2}. \quad (152)$$

If one had not made the assumption, with the existence of such n , the result for a_3 would have had one of these possible values:

$$a_3 = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \exists n \in \mathbb{N} \text{ s.t. } m = 3n \\ \frac{1}{m^2} & \text{if } \exists n \in \mathbb{N} \text{ s.t. } m = 3n + 1. \\ \frac{1}{2m^2} & \text{if } \exists n \in \mathbb{N} \text{ s.t. } m = 3n + 2 \end{cases} \quad (153)$$

Figure 11: Example of the invariance of the a_k w.r.t. m , for simple periodic time-series. It is easy to see that only a small interval of the spectrum is affected by the finite-size effect.

This behaviour for the time-scales is, of course, a result of the fact that, for a timescale Δt_k with $k \neq 1$, we add $\lfloor \frac{m^2}{k} \rfloor$ -times the k equally sized partitions of the unit cycle. For large m , the result of the first timescales therefore is negligible, even though $\frac{m^2}{k} > \lfloor \frac{m^2}{k} \rfloor$, and practically zero, because the small contributions are dwarfed by the normalisation.

For the other orders the same follows in the case of $m \rightarrow \infty$ and the resulting AvIT-Expansion (in its representation as a function) for the time-series $T_m = \{\Delta t, 2\Delta t, 3\Delta t, \dots, m\Delta t\}$ yields

$$\alpha_{T_m}(t) = \cos\left(\frac{2\pi t}{\Delta t}\right). \quad (154)$$

Now, since one sums over k equal partitions of the unit cycle for all time-scales Δt_k with $k \neq 1$, it is clear that this is only obtained in the limit $m \rightarrow \infty$. For any case of real finite data $\exists l, 1 < l < m \in \mathbb{N}$ s.t. $a_l > 0$, since one doesn't sum over the entire unit cycle any longer, for high Terms of a_k .

From simulations, one can see that in this simple periodic case, $\max_{l>1} a_l \approx 0.07$ with $l \approx 0.7m$ (see fig. 11). Since l scales linearly with m , it is clear that with $m \rightarrow \infty$, this term doesn't contribute to the sum. All the other $a_k > 0$ with $k > 1$ share a similar faith, since they also scale linear w.r.t. m .

Although it is analytically hard to show, it should be intuitively clear that this is an effect coming from the finite amount of data and has no deeper physical or mathematical reason; one might call this a windowing effect, I will call it the **finite-size** effect.

That this is an artifact is also clear when considering the intuition behind the coefficients, $a_{[0.7m]}$ would have the physical meaning that a value correlates with its neighbour after around 70% of the values from the time-series are skipped. It is clear that for values t_i with $i > 0.3m$, this neighbour is outside of the obtained data. Therefore, when analysing finite data with the AvIT-Expansion, one should always consider the physical meaning of the a_k . Also, when obtaining the end result of the AvIT-Expansion (eq. 137), the result might be

Figure 12: Example of the finite-size effect on the AvIT-Expansion. The underlying event-based time-series T_{100} is of length $m = 100$ and simple periodic with $\Delta t = 1$. The used threshold for the red graph was $\Delta t_{\text{physical}} = 10$. The result is shown over 20 periods. Although the result might suggest convergence, this is not the case and for t larger than shown here, one expects that the curves diverge more again.

influenced by this finite-size effect. One might have to introduce a threshold $\Delta t_{\text{physical}}$, after which the coefficients a_k , corresponding to time-scales above the threshold, are not considered when calculating the series. This is at best a timescale which is too large for the physical background anyway. The effect of (not) using the threshold can be best seen in fig. 12.

3.3.3. Examples

Although we already discussed the result for the simple periodic case, which was quite similar to those of the OM and CCM, let us examine more examples to see how the AvIT-Expansion performs with more difficult cases.

First, I will focus on the example of the same TFP, with whom I already tested the OM (fig. 8) and the CCM (fig. 4), i.e. a time-series with the two characteristic time-scales $\Delta t_1 = 10$ and $\Delta t_2 = 1$. The results for the expansion over the same time domain of the TFP and the spectrum can be seen here (fig. 13).

From this figure, one can see that the spectrum and the expansion recover two frequencies for this TFP. The first being the average frequency $1/\Delta t_{\text{avg}} = 0.1818'$ and the second is half

Figure 13: AvIT-Expansion of a TPF (with $\Delta t_1 = 10$ and $\Delta t_2 = 1$) (left) and the respective spectrum (right), obtained by plotting the series coefficients over the inverse time-scales. The series was calculated without the finite-size effect, disregarding frequencies smaller than 0.05. On the time-scale depicted here, the finite-size effect would be minimal anyway. The expected frequencies are marked in orange.

that frequency with $1/2\Delta t_{\text{avg}} = 0.0909'$. The second frequency is more profound in the spectrum than the first one. Since this frequency corresponds to a_2 , the intuitive meaning of the AvIT-Expansion tells us that we are dealing with a dynamic in which an underlying process happens every two events. Disregarding the recovered time-values, this intuition comes close to the construction of the TFP, since the distances between the events Δt_1 and Δt_2 alternates. Mathematically, it is also clear why $1/2\Delta t_{\text{avg}}$ achieved so high values, since $2\Delta t_{\text{avg}} = 1/0.0909' = 11$, which is just the sum of the time-scales, i.e. $\Delta t_1 + \Delta t_2$, and therefore one of the expected frequencies of the spectrum, as we discussed above. The other peak is then just the second harmonic of this peak.

The Expansion itself, as a continuous representation of the event-based time-series, shows the occurrence of two periodic maxima, following each other. To understand how this can be a representation of the event-based time-series, one can look the position of the global maxima, i.e. those local maxima with the highest amplitude. The maximas of the AvIT-Expansion can be found at the positions $(\alpha_{T_m}^{-1}(\max(\alpha_{T_m}))) = (0, 11, 22, 33, 44, 55, 66, 77, 88, 99, 110, \dots)$, when these time-stamps are compared to the underlying TFP

$$T_m = (0, 10, 11, 21, 22, 32, 33, 43, 44, 54, 55, 65, 66, 76, 77, 87, 88, 98, 99, 109, 110), \quad (155)$$

one can see that the maxima always align with one of the events. Therefore, the AvIT-Expansion can be naively understood as some sort of potential that, when reaching a specific threshold, triggers events. This is merely an intuition though, since the topic of back-transformation, although it is interesting and probably important in order to grasp the entire nature of event-based time-series, will not be investigated in this work.

From this very simple example, one can see the prominent problems occurring when working with the AvIT-Expansion. The method that calculates whether a time-scale is fitting to this event-data seems to be working well, but the problem is the set of possible time-scales

$(\Delta t_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, m\}}$ itself. Although it is computationally simple and stable to focus on the average time-scales of the system, the case of the TFP shows that, by using them, it is impossible to capture the smaller time-scales even in this very idealistic case. The other prominent issue is the resolution in the time/frequency domain. By limiting the calculation to the intuition, that only processes whose characteristic time-scales happen to be a natural number times the average inter-event time are allowed, the set of time-scales, and therefore the resolution, is sparse. I investigate these issues in the following section.

3.3.4. Alternative Approaches

Here, I want to address the first issue. As explained above, this comes from the choice of the average inter-event times. Another Ansatz would be to choose the average inter-event frequencies instead. This set can be defined with the following map:

$$\Delta f_{T_m} : \mathcal{S}_m^<(\mathbb{R}) \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_{m-1}^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \quad (156)$$

$$T_m \mapsto (\Delta f_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, m-1\}} = \left(k \sum_{i=1}^{m-1} \frac{\delta f_i}{m-1} \right) = \left(k \sum_{i=1}^{m-1} \frac{1}{\frac{t_{i+1}-t_i}{m-1}} \right)_{k \in \{1, \dots, m-1\}}. \quad (157)$$

Mathematically, one can see that this is just the inverse harmonic mean of the inter-event times, i.e. $1/\mu_{\text{harmonic}}((\delta t_i)_{i \in \{1, \dots, m-1\}})$ (see the proof here subsec. A.4) and therefore this discussion is focused on the difference of the choice between means (arithmetic and harmonic) on the results. I will denote the set of expansion coefficients, which are calculated with the average inter-event frequencies, with $(a_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, m-1\}}$ and the resulting AvIT-Expansion function with $\alpha_{T_m}^{\text{harm.}}(t)$.

It is well known that for any time-series $(u_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, m\}} \in \mathcal{S}_m(\mathbb{R})$, the means follow this inequality:

$$\mu_{\text{harmonic}}((u_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, m\}}) \leq \mu((u_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, m\}}). \quad (158)$$

This, of course, then leads to

$$\frac{1}{\Delta f_k} \leq \Delta t_k \quad \forall \Delta f_k \in \Delta f_{T_m}(T_m), \Delta t_k \in \Delta t_{T_m}(T_m). \quad (159)$$

For the resolution problem, the case $k = 1$ is of special importance. In the TFP example of the prior section, they actually follow $\Delta f_1 = 20\Delta t_1$, i.e. $1/\Delta f_1 = 1.81818'$ and $\Delta t_1 = 5.5$. The corresponding spectrum and AvIT-Expansion can be seen here fig. 14: When comparing these two results (fig. 13, fig. 14), the most obvious difference is their spectra. The AvIT-Expansion calculated with the harmonic mean starts with higher frequency values, with the first (corresponding to the inter-event time of 1.818') having no contribution to the result. This is noteworthy, since $1/\Delta t_1 = 1$ is one of the expected frequencies and 1.818' is close to it and its second harmonic. The next frequency, however, corresponding to the inter-event time 3.636', has a larger contribution. This result is unexpected, considering that none of the inter-event distances has this value. The rest of the spectrum looks similar, with two maxima, the first (at position 0.1833') close to the average inter-event time and the second (at position 0.0916667) in the neighbourhood of the other expected peak at $1/(\Delta t_1 + \Delta t_2)$.

Figure 14: AvIT-Expansion of a TPF (with $\Delta t_1 = 10$ and $\Delta t_2 = 1$) (left) and the respective spectrum (right), using the harmonic mean to determine the inter-event frequencies. The series was calculated without the finite-size effect, disregarding frequencies smaller than 0.05. The expected frequencies are marked in orange.

Figure 15: Spectrum of the AvIT-Expansion of a TPF (with $\Delta t_1 = 10$ and $\Delta t_2 = 1$), calculated with the arithmetic mean (left) and the harmonic mean (right). Both were calculated with a resolution coefficient $z = 100$. The expected frequencies are marked in orange.

When discussing the differences of the corresponding AvIT-Expansions, one can see that one calculated with the harmonic mean features a second local maximum in between the global ones. Apart from that, though, the AvIT-Expansions are pretty similar. Both of them can be understood as continuous representations with the same intuition, we discussed before. For the resolution problem, one can also try another approach by allowing non-natural multiples of the mean inter-event times. This is achieved by introducing a resolution factor $\iota \in \mathbb{N}$ and mapping the original sequence of time-scales $(\Delta t_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, m-1\}}$ in this way:

$$\Delta t_{T_m}^\iota : \mathcal{S}_{m-1}^< \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_{\iota(m-1)}^< \quad (160)$$

$$(\Delta t_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, m-1\}} \mapsto (\Delta t_j^\iota)_{j \in \{1, \dots, \iota(m-1)\}} = \left(\frac{j}{\iota} \Delta t_1 \right)_{j \in \{1, \dots, \iota(m-1)\}}. \quad (161)$$

Analogously this is done with the sequence of average frequencies $(\Delta f_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, m-1\}}$ leading to the sequence $(\Delta f_j^\iota)_{j \in \{1, \dots, \iota(m-1)\}}$. With this, a new set of coefficients $(a_j^\iota)_{j \in \{1, \dots, \iota(m-1)\}}$ or $(\tilde{a}_j^\iota)_{j \in \{1, \dots, \iota(m-1)\}}$ is calculated with these new time-scales, analogously to (eq. 143). This is a very naive approach, producing many difficulties. This can be best seen in the example of the TFP I used above (fig. 15).

Here, one can clearly see that these spectra have broader peaks and the left spectrum is identifiable as the left half of the right spectrum. The peaks are broadened as ι was increased, as expected, which led to difficulties when calculating the continuous representation (fig. 16). Here, these many frequencies with coefficients significantly above zero, i.e. the broadening in frequency space, lead to a representation which does not resemble the underlying event-based time-series anymore. That this is an effect of the broadening can be seen by increasing the data points in T_m , which leads to sharpening of the peaks in the spectrum. In this case the AvIT-Expansions looks more like the example before (fig. 14, fig. 13). This, of course, is a problem, considering that in a real physical system, one might not have the ability to just increase the data points.

To summarize, in this section, I tried to solve the resolution problems of the AvIT-Expansion with various effects. While the usage of the harmonic mean had promising results, the introduction of a resolution factor led to a situation in which this parameter had to be carefully chosen by the user. One could try to investigate this further by, instead of looking at the means, using time-scales calculated from the distribution of the inter-event times or all values of the distance matrix from the time-series T_m , like quartiles and the median. I, however, focus in the following section on another method, which uses a similar approach to the AvIT-Expansion, but has some significant advantages, which eliminate these problems beforehand.

Figure 16: Expansion functions of the AvIT-Expansion of a TPF (with $\Delta t_1 = 10$ and $\Delta t_2 = 1$), calculated with the arithmetic mean (left) and the harmonic mean (right). Both were calculated with a resolution coefficient $\nu = 100$ and a disregarding of frequencies smaller than 0.05

3.4. Approximation of Continuous Representations using the LANGE-Expansion

Another theoretical approach to the field of (series) expansions is to choose an orthogonal (usually also orthonormal) basis of the space in question and expand the mathematical object in this basis. This is e.g. the case for the expansion of a function, with the Fourier series or the Taylor series. I introduced the AvIT-Expansion, by defining that the continuous functions I use for the expansion are just functions of the function space $\mathcal{F}(\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{R})$, without further limitations. One can argue that this *ad hoc* approach, due to the fact that I did not care to establish on which exact space, with which scalar product and with which basis I am working, led to mathematical artifacts and difficulties later on. To recall: the main issues for the AvIT-Expansion were the finite-size effect (fig. 12) and the overall resolution of the frequency space (fig. 15, fig. 16), especially the resolution of high frequencies (fig. 13, fig. 14).

I will start this section by defining that for an event-based time-series $T_m \in \mathcal{S}_m^<(\mathbb{R}^+)$, with start value t_1 and end value t_m , the space that I am working on, is the space of integrable and square-integrable periodic functions $\mathcal{P}([t_1, t_m], \mathbb{R})$. To clarify, periodic here means that the functions are actually defined on the entire real numbers \mathbb{R} , but with a period of at least $t_m + t_1$. This means that $\forall f \in \mathcal{P}([t_1, t_m], \mathbb{R})$ follows $f(t) = f(t + t_m - t_1)$. Therefore, one can limit the definition of \mathcal{P} to functions which map from $[t_1, t_m]$ (or equivalently $[0, t_m - t_1]$) to \mathbb{R} (instead of $\mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$), since no additional information would be gained by including all real numbers.

In this space, I define a **inner product** as the following map:

$$\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle : \mathcal{P}([t_1, t_m], \mathbb{R}) \times \mathcal{P}([t_1, t_m], \mathbb{R}) \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \quad (162)$$

$$(p(t), q(t)) \mapsto \langle p, q \rangle = \int_{t_1}^{t_m} p(t)q(t)dt. \quad (163)$$

The proof that the space $\mathcal{P}([t_1, t_m], \mathbb{R})$ equipped with this inner product is indeed an inner product space $(\mathcal{P}, \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle)$ can be seen here (subsec. A.5). One can also prove that $\mathcal{P}([t_1, t_m], \mathbb{R})$ is complete, i.e. every Cauchy sequence of functions converges. This can be done by using the Chebyshev inequality, Riesz theorem and the Fatou lemma, like Castillo did in his book for Theorem 1.14 [16]. Although he proves the completeness for $L_2(\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{R})$ (the space of square-integrable functions on \mathbb{R}), the proof for $\mathcal{P}([t_1, t_m], \mathbb{R})$ would be analogous, since the Chebyshev inequality, Riesz theorem and the Fatou lemma are all defined for functions on spaces $X \subset \mathbb{R}$ [16].

With this inner product (eq. 162), one can proof that the expansion functions of the AvIT-Expansion are not orthogonal on the space $L_2([t_m, t_1], \mathbb{R}) \cap L_1([t_m, t_1], \mathbb{R})$ (one has to limited the function to these spaces, since they are not necessarily periodic w.r.t. $t_m - t_1$, therefore these functions are in general not part of the space $\mathcal{P}([t_1, t_m], \mathbb{R})$ and since they are in general not integrable or square-integrable on \mathbb{R} , they can not be element of $L_2(\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{R})$ either). The proof can be found in the appendix (subsec. A.6).

With this, I established that the expansion is based on functions of the inner product space $(\mathcal{P}, \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle)$. I also demand that these expansion functions are orthogonal. I do this with the knowledge that the basis functions of the AvIT-Expansion are unsuitable, since they are not part of $\mathcal{P}([t_1, t_m], \mathbb{R})$ and not orthogonal on $(L_2 \cap L_1, \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle)$.

With this in mind, I define this second expansion in the following subsection.

3.4.1. Definition

The intuition behind this second series expansion approach is the following: I choose a small frequency δf as the "sampling frequency" and then sample through the entire frequency space (i.e. $f = k \cdot \delta f$), until a limit $f_g = M \cdot \delta f$ is reached, which is given by the event-based time-series $T_m \in \mathcal{S}_m^<(\mathbb{R}^+)$ (or the physical context).

For this I make use of the sampling theorem (see (eq. 37), [13] or [14]) and its dual version. This states that for the "sampling frequency" δf I have to choose $\delta f \leq \frac{1}{t_m - t_1}$ ([13]). so I choose $\delta f = \frac{1}{t_m - t_1}$. In a continuous picture, the maximal frequency should be chosen so that $f_g = \frac{1}{T}$ ([17]), since in the continuous context T is the distance between sampled time-steps. However, since I work with event-based time-series, I chose that T is just the smallest of distances between events $\Delta t_{\min}^{T_m}$ (formally defined in (eq. 102)). So with the choice of

$f_g = \frac{1}{\Delta t_{\min}^{T_m}}$, the integer M to fulfill $f_g = M \cdot \delta f$, has to be chosen as $M = \left\lceil \frac{t_m - t_1}{\Delta t_{\min}^{T_m}} \right\rceil$.

With all this work done, I define the **LANGE-Expansion** (LE) with the following map:

$$\mathcal{L}_m : \mathcal{S}_n^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \times \mathcal{S}_m^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \rightarrow \Pi_n \quad (164)$$

$$((t_i)_{i \in \{1, \dots, n\}}, T_m) \mapsto \mathcal{L}_n(T_m) = (t_i, \ell_{T_m}(t_i))_{i \in \{1, \dots, n\}}. \quad (165)$$

With the real **LANGE-Function** (LF) $\ell_{T_m}(t)$ defined by the following map:

$$\ell_m : \mathcal{S}_m^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \rightarrow \mathcal{P}([t_1, t_m], \mathbb{R}) \quad (166)$$

$$T_m \mapsto \ell_{T_m}(t) = \sum_{k=1}^M \lambda_k \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi(t - t_1)}{t_m - t_1}\right). \quad (167)$$

I will denote a basis function of the LF which corresponds to the coefficient λ_k (i.e. $\cos\left(\frac{2k\pi(t-t_1)}{t_m-t_1}\right)$) with $c_k(t)$ or simply c_k . Note that the term "basis functions" should not imply that those functions are a full orthonormal basis of the space, but rather the underlying functions used in the expansion.

The integer M is formally defined as:

$$M : \mathcal{S}_m^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \rightarrow \mathbb{N} \quad (168)$$

$$T_m \mapsto M \text{ s.t. } M - 1 < \frac{t_m - t_1}{\Delta t_{\min}^{T_m}} \leq M. \quad (169)$$

The coefficients λ_k are obtained by this map:

$$\lambda_{T_m} : \mathcal{S}_m^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_M^<([-1, 1]) \quad (170)$$

$$T_m \mapsto (\lambda_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, M\}} = \left(\frac{1}{m^2} \sum_{i,j=1}^m \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi(t_i - t_j)}{t_m - t_1}\right) \right). \quad (171)$$

The difference to the AvIT-Expansion is clearly visible in these formulas and the intuition or idea behind the formulas. The AvIT-Expansion samples through a set of averaged timescales present in the time-series, to determine the relevant underlying frequencies, while the LE samples through the entire frequency space.

For the definitions, I used the sampling theorems and stated that the LF is an element of the inner product space $(\mathcal{P}, \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle)$, but did not check whether the basis functions of the expansion are orthogonal. In the following, I will focus on these two concerns.

First, I have to show that any general LF is an element of $\mathcal{P}([t_1, t_m], \mathbb{R})$. Since the LFs are (as sums of cosine terms) defined on \mathbb{R} and therefore also on $[t_1, t_m]$, I have to show only their periodicity, i.e. $l_{T_m}(t) = l_{T_m}(t + t_m - t_1)$.

$$l_{T_m}(t + t_m - t_1) = \sum_{k=1}^M \lambda_k \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi(t + t_m - t_1 - t_1)}{t_m - t_1}\right) \quad (172)$$

$$= \sum_{k=1}^M \lambda_k \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi(t - t_1)}{t_m - t_1} + \frac{2k\pi(t_m - t_1)}{t_m - t_1}\right) \quad (173)$$

$$= \sum_{k=1}^M \lambda_k \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi(t - t_1)}{t_m - t_1} + 2k\pi\right) \quad (174)$$

$$= \sum_{k=1}^M \lambda_k \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi(t - t_1)}{t_m - t_1}\right) \quad (175)$$

$$= l_{T_m}(t). \quad (176)$$

Now I have to check for orthogonality of the basis functions. So, $\forall k \neq j \in \{1, \dots, M\}$ follows $\langle c_k, c_j \rangle = 0$.

$$\langle c_k, c_j \rangle = \int_{t_1}^{t_m} \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi(t-t_1)}{t_m-t_1}\right) \cos\left(\frac{2j\pi(t-t_1)}{t_m-t_1}\right) dt \quad (177)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \int_{t_1}^{t_m} \left[\cos\left(\frac{2(k+j)\pi(t-t_1)}{t_m-t_1}\right) + \cos\left(\frac{2(k-j)\pi(t-t_1)}{t_m-t_1}\right) \right] dt \quad (178)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \left[\left[\frac{t_m-t_1}{2(k+j)\pi(t-t_1)} \sin\left(\frac{2(k+j)\pi(t-t_1)}{t_m-t_1}\right) + \frac{t_m-t_1}{2(k-j)\pi(t-t_1)} \sin\left(\frac{2(k-j)\pi(t-t_1)}{t_m-t_1}\right) \right]_{t_1}^{t_m} \right] \quad (179)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{t_m-t_1}{2(k+j)\pi(t-t_1)} \sin\left(\frac{2(k+j)\pi(t_m-t_1)}{t_m-t_1}\right) + \frac{t_m-t_1}{2(k-j)\pi(t-t_1)} \sin\left(\frac{2(k-j)\pi(t_m-t_1)}{t_m-t_1}\right) \right] \quad (180)$$

$$= 0. \quad (181)$$

Since $k \pm j \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\sin(2n\pi) = 0 \forall n \in \mathbb{N}$.

One can see that $\langle c_k, c_k \rangle = 1$ by inserting $k = j$ in the second line of that proof, i.e.

$$\langle c_k, c_k \rangle = \frac{1}{2} \int_{t_1}^{t_m} \left[1 + \cos\left(\frac{4\pi(t-t_1)}{t_m-t_1}\right) \right] dt \quad (182)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \left[(t_m-t_1) + \left[\frac{t_m-t_1}{4\pi(t-t_1)} \sin\left(\frac{4\pi(t-t_1)}{t_m-t_1}\right) \right]_{t_1}^{t_m} \right] \quad (183)$$

$$= \frac{t_m-t_1}{2}. \quad (184)$$

Which leads to

$$\langle c_k, c_j \rangle = \frac{t_m-t_1}{2} \delta_{kj}. \quad (185)$$

With the Kronecker-Delta $\delta_{kj} = 1$ if $k = j \wedge \delta_{kj} = 0$ if $k \neq j$. One could normalise the basis functions, i.e. $\tilde{c}_j = \frac{\sqrt{2}c_j}{\sqrt{t_m-t_1}}$, to obtain a orthonormal set of basis functions. However, I chose not to do that, so that spectra from different event-based time-series (with different duration times) can be compared better. Since, without normalisation, these coefficients are just bound by -1 and 1.

With these two issues out of the way, I expect that the LE won't suffer from the finite-size effect and resolution problems.

At this point, I emphasize the theoretical assumptions that one makes when performing such a series expansion. As stated above, the LE is calculated by sampling through all possible frequencies to determine the frequencies of the underlying processes. In the case that the expansion coefficient λ_k , corresponding to a frequency ω_k , is larger than zero, the time-evolution of the amplitude $\Lambda_k(t) = \lambda_k \cos(\omega_k t)$ is added to the amplitudes of all the other processes, eventually forming the LF $\ell(t) = \sum_{k=1}^N \Lambda_k(t)$. In this simple picture, it is clear

that I implicitly assumed a linear relationship in the interactions of the processes. A 0-th order approximation in the time-evolution of the phase $\varphi_k(t)$, i.e. $\dot{\varphi}_k = \omega_k + \mathcal{O}(t)$, is the second assumption made here. This is a first-order, i.e. linear, approximation of the phase $\varphi_k(t)$. This can be justified only by the assumption that higher-order contributions are small compared to the timescale $t_m - t_1$ or that the overall process is in some sort of equilibrium. While the first assumption can be justified easily (in most cases), with the explanation that the amplitudes Λ_k must not be mapped to isolated underlying physical processes, but could correspond to some effective processes (i.e. resulting from e.g. non-linear interactions between underlying physical processes), the second assumption should always be kept in mind when working with the LE and should be tested by e.g. performing the LE on subsets of the event-based time-series, to see whether the results differ.

With the promise that this method (in contrast to the AvIT-Expansion) is able to be performed on any non-trivial general event-based time-series, I call this method the **Linear phase-Approximation of Non-trivial General Event-data** (LANGE), with the addition of either "Expansion" (LE) or "Function" (LF) to highlight which mathematical object referenced.

With this out of the way, I want to address some nuances of the inner product, its space and the consequences for the LE.

The way I defined the inner product (eq. 162), I can calculate it only with such functions f, g , which have the same periodicity of $t_m - t_1$. Therefore it is only possible to calculate a overlap of two LFs $\ell_{T_m}(t), \ell_{\mathcal{T}_n}(t)$ using this inner product, if the two corresponding event-based time-series T_m, \mathcal{T}_n have the same duration, i.e. $t_m^{T_m} - t_1^{T_m} = t_n^{\mathcal{T}_n} - t_1^{\mathcal{T}_n}$. In this case, however, one can represent the LFs as M and M' dimensional vectors (or as sequences in $\mathcal{S}_M(\mathbb{R})$ and $\mathcal{S}_{M'}(\mathbb{R})$) and calculate the scalar product, intuitively with

$$\langle \ell_{T_m}, \ell_{\mathcal{T}_n} \rangle = \frac{t_m - t_1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^{\min\{M, M'\}} \lambda_k^{T_m} \lambda_k^{\mathcal{T}_n}. \quad (186)$$

The proof is rather simple and can be seen in the appendix (subsec. A.7).

At this point, I want to emphasize that the LE and AvIT-Expansion are meant to be substitutes for the underlying continuous time-series of an event-based time-series. Therefore, typical time-series analysis tools may be used on the AvIT-Expansion and the LE. The LE has multiple advantages compared to the AvIT-Expansion, due to the fact that it has a solid theoretical foundation. An example of the helpfulness of this solid theoretical foundation and of a typical continuous time-series analysis tool is the autocorrelation function.

With this scalar product, one can easily define an ACF on this space, analogous to the classical definition (eq. 27):

$$R_f : \mathcal{P}([t_1, t_m], \mathbb{R}) \rightarrow \mathcal{P}([t_1, t_m], \mathbb{R}) \quad (187)$$

$$f(t) \mapsto R_f(\tau) = \frac{1}{|\langle f, f \rangle|} \langle f, f(t + \tau) \rangle. \quad (188)$$

With this, one can calculate the ACF of the LF in the general case and obtain this analytical formula (for details, see the proof in the appendix subsec. A.8):

$$R_{\ell_{t_m}}(\tau) = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^M \lambda_k^2 c_k(\tau)}{\sum_{k=1}^M \lambda_k^2}. \quad (189)$$

This analytic result may simplify working with the LE, since the ACF is a commonly used tool for a variety of algorithms, e.g. the phase-space reconstruction using Tarkin's Theorem [11]. With this result, it is possible to reconstruct the ACF analytically from already known quantities, without additional calculation.

With all of this theoretical work done, I will discuss the spectral analysis in the next section.

3.4.2. Spectral Analysis

I will test the spectral analysis using the LE on the case of the simple periodic event-timeseries $T_m = \{\Delta t, 2\Delta t, 3\Delta t, \dots, m\Delta t\}$, here $t_m - t_1 = (m-1)\Delta t$.

As calculated above, the AvIT-Expansion for $m \rightarrow \infty$ yields $\alpha_{T_m}(t) = \cos\left(\frac{2\pi(t-t_1)}{\Delta t}\right)$ in this case. Now, let us investigate whether the results differ for the LE.

When writing the definition of the λ_k (eq. 170) as a sum over all the elements of the following matrix:

$$\frac{1}{m^2} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{m-1}\right) & \cos\left(\frac{4k\pi}{m-1}\right) & \dots & \cos(2k\pi) \\ \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{m-1}\right) & 1 & \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{m-1}\right) & \dots & \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi(m-2)}{m-1}\right) \\ \cos\left(\frac{4k\pi}{m-1}\right) & \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{m-1}\right) & 1 & \dots & \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi(m-3)}{m-1}\right) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \cos(2k\pi) & \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi(m-2)}{m-1}\right) & \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi(m-3)}{m-1}\right) & \dots & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (190)$$

one can see that the λ_k can be expressed as:

$$\lambda_k = \frac{1}{m} + \frac{2}{m^2} \sum_{l=1}^{m-1} (m-l) \cos\left(\frac{2kl\pi}{m-1}\right). \quad (191)$$

This is due to the high symmetry of this double sum, in this simple case.

It can indeed be analytically shown that this sum converges to the same result as the AvIT-Expansion. Without the limit $m \rightarrow \infty$ the coefficients λ_m are determined by (see proof in appendix (subsec. A.9)):

$$\lambda_{m-1} = 1 \quad (192)$$

$$\lambda_k = \frac{1}{m^2}, \quad \forall k \neq m-1. \quad (193)$$

From that, one can see that in the limit the LF behaves like this:

$$\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \ell_{T_m}(t) = \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{k=1}^{m-1} \lambda_k \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi(t-t_1)}{(m-1)\Delta t}\right) \quad (194)$$

$$= \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \left(\cos\left(\frac{2\pi(t-t_1)}{\Delta t}\right) + \sum_{k=2}^{m-1} \frac{1}{m^2} \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi t}{(m-1)\Delta t}\right) \right) \quad (195)$$

$$\leq \cos\left(\frac{2\pi(t-t_1)}{\Delta t}\right) + \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{m^2} \sum_{k=2}^{m-1} \quad (196)$$

$$= \cos\left(\frac{2\pi(t-t_1)}{\Delta t}\right) + \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \frac{m-1}{m^2} \quad (197)$$

$$= \cos\left(\frac{2\pi(t-t_1)}{\Delta t}\right). \quad (198)$$

So in the limit, it follows that for the simple periodic case:

$$\ell_{T_\infty}(t) = \alpha_{T_\infty}(t). \quad (199)$$

When comparing the coefficients of the AvIT- and the LANGE-Expansion for this case directly, one can see that:

$$a_1 = \lambda_{m-1}, \quad (200)$$

$$a_{m-1} = \lambda_1. \quad (201)$$

In fact, this holds true for all time-series just by the definition of the coefficients (eq. 143, eq. 170), immediately raising the question whether other terms of the expansions align as well. However, with further investigations, it becomes clear that this is not the case (see the proof in the appendix (subsec. A.10)).

After this I continue the analysis of the simple periodic case. In contrast to the AvIT-Expansion, the LANGE-Expansion indeed does not suffer from a finite size effect (fig. 17) and therefore one does not need to introduce a physical cut-off in the spectrum. With this simple spectral analysis done, let us turn our attention to the more complex examples, which I already used to test the other methods.

3.4.3. The LANGE-Expansion - Examples

Again, I will use the TFP with the characteristic time-scales $\Delta t_1 = 10$ and $\Delta t_2 = 1$. First, I focus on the LF of this case (fig. 18). As one can see, the first maximum corresponds to the first event ($\Delta t_1 = 10$), while the following maximum corresponds to the follow-up event ($\Delta t_2 = 1$). To extract the event-based time-series from that, one would have to collect the time of local maxima, after thresholding the amplitude of the time-series at a value of 3. Through calculating the LF for times $t \gg t_m$, one can see that the local maxima that appear in the left graph before the main maxima (and which do not correspond to an event-time in the data) are never larger than 3, justifying the choice of this threshold.

Figure 17: Spectrum and LF for simple periodic time-series with $m = 73$ and $\Delta t = 1$. The LF is shown over 20 periods.

Figure 18: LF for a TFP with time-scales $\Delta t_1 = 1$, $\Delta t_2 = 10$ and $m = 100$, for two different time-intervals. The first graph (left) shows the LF over the duration of the given data, while the second (right) graph shows the transition between local maxima.

Figure 19: LF for a TFP with time-scales $\Delta t_1 = 1$, $\Delta t_2 = 10$ and $m = 100$, for times $t > 1000$. The transitions and the respective increase or decrease of multiple amplitudes can be observed on this large timescale.

The right graph shows that the LF has an interesting dynamic, in which the amplitude of the first maxima decreases, while the second one increases. In the depicted interval, one can witness the transition in which the first maxima is smaller than the second time for the first time. When calculating the LF for times $t > 1000$ (fig. 19), one can see that this is a periodic process, but with a way larger period than the event-based time-series suggests.

To explain this, let us picture the LF in the following as a simple cosine with frequency $f = 1$, but with the slight difference that the local maxima have a transition dynamic every 11 local maxima (called "amplitudes" from now on). In these amplitude "packages" $(A_1(t), A_2(t), \dots, A_{11}(t))$, two amplitudes $(A_n(t)$ and $A_{n+1}(t))$ are always above the event-threshold, corresponding to the events depicted in the underlying event-based time-series. For the explanation, let us suppose that at time t_0 $A_n(t_0) > A_{n+1}(t_0)$. Also, at least 5 consecutive amplitudes are always increasing (in the sense that $\forall t \in \mathbb{R}^+ \exists l \in \mathbb{N}$ s.t. $\frac{d}{dt} A_{\text{mod}_{11}(l+j)}(t) > 0 \forall j \in \mathbb{N} 0 \leq j \leq 5$), while at least 5 consecutive amplitudes are always decreasing. After a time of $t_{\text{trans.}}/4 = 1090/4$ the amplitude A_n is no longer larger than its successor, i.e. $A_n(t_0 + t_{\text{trans.}}/4) < A_{n+1}(t_0 + t_{\text{trans.}}/4)$ and after the same duration is the amplitude A_n below the threshold of 3, i.e. $A_n(t_0 + t_{\text{trans.}}/2) < 3$. The amplitude $A_{n+2}(t)$, however, is now above the threshold and will continue to increase. At the same time, the amplitude A_{n+1} reaches its maximum. After that, the amplitude A_{n+1} starts its decrease. At $t = t_0 + 3t_{\text{trans.}}/4$ the amplitude A_{n+1} will be smaller than A_{n+2} and after the time $t = t_0 + t_{\text{trans.}}$ is the amplitude A_{n+1} below the threshold, while A_{n+2} reaches its maximum and then starts its decline.

Figure 20: Spectrum and time-scales for a TFP with time-scales $\Delta t_1 = 1$, $\Delta t_2 = 10$ and length $m = 100$. The expected frequencies are marked in orange. The equally sampled LE is able to recover every major frequency of the process and its harmonics and subharmonics.

To conclude, in any given interval $[t_0, t_0 + 11t_{\text{trans}}]$ all amplitudes will spend a duration of $\Delta t = t_{\text{trans}}$ above the threshold. As one can see, this process has a periodicity of $11t_{\text{trans}}$, which is way larger than the longest time given in the event-based time-series.

After this discussion, I will focus on the spectrum (fig. 20).

One can see that the LE was able to recover the two important frequencies $f = 1$ (in contrast to the AvIT-Expansion) and $f = 1/11$. From these frequencies is the TFP fully recoverable. As explained above, the frequencies correspond to $\Delta t_1 = 1$ and $\Delta_1 + \Delta t_2 = 11$, which are the two expected time-scales to be recovered from the spectrum.

The other present frequencies are just harmonics or subharmonics of these two underlying frequencies, which can easily seen in the plot of the time-scales on the right. When reading from right to left, one can see that the maximum is at 11, the next value is at 5.5 (second subharmonic), followed by 3.6' (third subharmonic), 2.75 (fourth subharmonic) and 2.2 (fifth subharmonic). When reading the spectrum (left) from left to right, the first maxima is at $1/11 = 0.09'$, the next is at $0.18'$ (second harmonic), followed by $0.27'$ (third harmonic), $0.36'$ (fourth harmonic) and $0.45'$ (fifth harmonic). The appearance of (sub-) harmonics is quite common in the analysis of spectra and not an issue related to this method.

The LE fully satisfied the aim to recover the frequencies of the TFP. But before I test all of the algorithms and methods on real data, let us explore alternative definitions for the LE in the following subchapter.

3.4.4. Alternative Definitions

As I already used for one of the proofs (subsec. A.8), the set of functions $c_k(t) = \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi(t-t_1)}{t_m-t_1}\right)$ are basis functions of the space $\mathcal{P}([t_1, t_m], \mathbb{R})$, however, do not form a complete basis. The other basis functions are $s_j(t) = \sin\left(\frac{2j\pi(t-t_1)}{t_m-t_1}\right)$ and $c_0 = 1$. So one might ask why I did not choose these functions for the expansion, in order to map on the entire space and not only

on a subspace.

For the constant function c_0 , this answer is easy. The corresponding coefficient always has the same values $\lambda_0 = 1$, due to the normalisation, and offers therefore no spectral information and is merely an offset for the LF.

For the other basis function, the intuitive answer is, that one wants to obtain a function, in which the maxima of the function correspond to the events from the event-based time-series. If one were to define the LANGE-Function as

$$l_m : \mathcal{S}_m^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \rightarrow \mathcal{P}([t_1, t_m], \mathbb{R}) \quad (202)$$

$$T_m \mapsto l_{T_m}(t) = \sum_{k=1}^M \lambda_k c_k(t) + \tilde{\lambda}_k s_k(t), \quad (203)$$

with the new coefficients $\tilde{\lambda}_k$ defined as

$$\tilde{\lambda}_{T_m} : \mathcal{S}_m^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_M^<([-1, 1]) \quad (204)$$

$$T_m \mapsto (\tilde{\lambda}_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, M\}} = \left(\frac{1}{m^2} \sum_{i,j=1}^m \sin \left(\frac{2k\pi(t_i - t_j)}{t_m - t_1} \right) \right), \quad (205)$$

the coefficients $\tilde{\lambda}_k$ would return zero if the inter-event distance of two events would fit the frequency $f_k = k/(t_m - t_1)$. For the simple periodic example, this is especially true, leading to no contribution from this basis function, i.e. the LF is inherently only defined on this subspace.

Apart from this example, the coefficients $\tilde{\lambda}_k$ defined in this way are also always zero or negligible. Although I will not proof this analytically, I show this by calculating the spectrum for an event-based time-series with random inter-event times (i.e. inter-event times are uniformly distributed in the interval $[0, 50]$) (fig. 22) and for the TFP I used earlier ($\Delta t_1 = 1, \Delta t_2 = 10$) (fig. 21), next to the results for the coefficients λ_k . I also tested the coefficients on the real-world data I use in the following section, with similar results. I therefore chose not to show them due to redundancy.

It is clear why I neglected the second and third base-function of the space $\mathcal{P}([t_1, t_m], \mathbb{R})$ in the original definition of the LF (eq. 166). For further research, it would be interesting to find an analytic reason why (and also an analytic proof that) the LF only maps onto this subspace.

But with these considerations out of the way, I will test all of the methods, the CCM, the OM, the AvIT-Expansion and the LANGE-Expansion on real data. I will explore this interesting part of the work in the next chapter.

Figure 21: Spectrum obtained from the maps λ_{T_m} (left) and $\tilde{\lambda}_{T_m}$ (right) for a TFP with time-scales $\Delta t_1 = 1$, $\Delta t_2 = 10$ and length $m = 100$. The spectrum on the right is in the order of 10^{-17} , indicating that the entire spectrum is a numerical artifact and analytically zero. Even if it is not a numerical artifact, it is drawn by the spectrum on the left, showing the irrelevance of the $\tilde{\lambda}_k$ contributions to the LF, in this case.

Figure 22: Spectrum obtained from an event-based time-series with random inter-event times (i.e. uniformly distributed in the interval $[0, 50]$) and length $m = 100$. The spectrum on the left shows the coefficients obtained from λ_{T_m} , with a spectrum typical for white-noise signals. The spectrum on the right is obtained from $\tilde{\lambda}_{T_m}$ and is also typical for white-noise, but 15 orders of magnitude lower than the spectrum on the left. Like in the case of (fig. 21) that the data is irrelevant compared to the spectrum on the left when computing the LF.

4. Testing the Novel Methods on Real-World Data

In this section, I test the methods I developed on geyser data from the Strokkur geyser in Iceland. The data was sampled and analysed by the team of Prof. Eibl from the University of Potsdam, Germany, together with a group around Prof. Dahm from GFZ Potsdam, Germany and Gylfi Páll Hersir from ISOR Iceland GeoSurvey Reykjavik, Iceland [7].

In their papers, they explained the mechanisms that cause the eruption of the geyser and the way they collected their data in a very detailed manner. I will limit myself to a brief overview, since I use the data as a mere illustration of the methods. Therefore, I want to emphasize that more detailed information on the background of the data can be found in [7], [18] and [19]. In the following, I first introduce the data set, before investigating the data with each of the novel methods.

4.1. Data Set

As described in their paper [18], the eruptive behaviour of the Strokkur is explainable with a cycle of 4 phases, which I will sketch briefly, before discussing the technicalities of the data. The content of the following part is taken from [19].

The first phase starts with a bubble slug, which reaches the surface and bursts. That way, water and steam are pushed upwards and erupt in the form of a water fountain. These eruptions can happen up to six times in quick succession. The phase ends with the end of the eruptions. The second phase starts with the refilling of the conduit, with water which exited the conduit in the previous eruption flowing back from the pool above and water from an aquifer that links the conduit horizontally with a bubble reservoir (the existence of this link was suggested based on seismic data by [18]). The loss of heat and water in the bubble reservoir during the first and second phase leads to the reservoir being filled with gas in the third phase. In the last phase of the cycle, these gases travel through the horizontal crack into the conduit and collapse in the much colder water. That way, these bubbles heat the water until the water is warm enough, so that the bubbles are not collapsing any longer and can travel to the surface. Now the cycle start again with the eruption, which empties the bubble reservoir of most of its gas, so that water can refill the reservoir from below [19].

Eibl et al. distinguish between 6 eruption types: single, double, triple, quadruple, quintuple and sextuple eruptions, corresponding to the number of eruptions during the first phase. The main difference between these types is their likelihood (with single eruptions being by far the most likely ones) and the their posteruption waiting times [7]. They show that this waiting time scales linearly with the number of eruptions [7], which was already suggested by Kieffer in 1984 [20]. Eibl et al. explain this with the heat transfer mechanism of the reservoir: since more energy is released by multiple eruptions and the heat is transferred linearly w.r.t. time, more time is needed for the water in the conduit to achieve its critical temperature [7].

The data of Eibl et al. records the eruption events of the geyser and starts with the first event on the 27th of June 2017 at 03:06:10 and ends with the last event on the 10th of June 2018 04:20:25. The measurements were conducted daily with a 24h recording time from

1st December 2017 to 28th January 2018 and a 10h recording time (midnight to 10 a.m. local time) from 27th June 2017 to 30th November 2017 and from the 29th January 2018 to the 7th June 2018. This limitation was done to ensure a good signal-to-noise ratio, due to daytime anthropogenic noise [21]. That way, 73,466 events were recorded [7]. Although I could've analysed the entire data set with the methods, I limited myself to the data of one week in December 2017, from the 1st to the 7th, to keep computational time low. That way, I was also able to avoid issues, which may be caused by the 10h recording time limitation. This also has the benefit that the assumption of linearity in the time-evolution of the underlying phases is much easier to defend on this relatively small subset of the entire data. With this temporal limitation, I was left with $K_{\text{subset}} = 2,836$ events. After that, I converted the original data, given in the format yyyy-mm-dd hh:mm:ss, into a sequence of time-values given in seconds.

Since the waiting time is dependend on the eruption type, I will now estimate the expected number of events for every eruption type in my subset. Eibl et al. found that the total number of n -tuple eruption N , has a exponential relationship to the number of eruptions per type n , following this distribution $\ln(N) = 13 - 2.15 \cdot n$. They state that they found 50,135 single eruptions, 9,683 double eruptions, 948 triple eruptions, 103 quadruple eruptions, 17 quintuple eruptions and 1 sextuple eruption [7]. Inteterestingly, this only adds up to 72,848 total events, with 618 events ($\approx 0.84\%$) remaining unclassified. A estimation of a probability that an event is attributed to a n -tuple eruption (which I call $p(n)$), can be calculated with this

$$p(n) = \frac{N(n) \cdot n}{\sum_{i=1}^6 N(i) + 618}. \quad (206)$$

This leads to: $p(1) \approx 68.24\%$, $p(2) \approx 26.36\%$, $p(3) \approx 3.87\%$, $p(4) \approx 0.56\%$, $p(5) \approx 0.12\%$ and $p(6) \approx 0.01\%$. Therefore, I would expect that my 2,836 events consist of ≈ 1935 single, ≈ 748 double, ≈ 110 triple, ≈ 16 quadruple and ≈ 3 quintuple eruption events. Also, about 24 events of this subset are expected to be unclassified. In the following I will use $M(n)$ to refer to these numbers.

Since the documentation of one these multituple events require that $M(n)/n \in \mathbb{N}$, I correct my numbers to 111 triple and 0 quintuple events.

Therefore, I expect to find only the corresponding preeruption t_{pre} , posteruption t_{post} and intraeruption times t_{intra} of the single, double, triple and quadruple events in my data. With the preeruption time being defined as the time before an n -tuple eruption and the posteruption time being the time after an n -tuple eruption, the intraeruption time is defined as the time between the first and the last event of a multituple eruption [7]. The means of these times for the different eruption types are listed in tab. 1.

The high uncertainty of these characteristic times and the fact that their uncertainty intervals overlap in some cases, makes it difficult to attribute single peaks from a corresponding spectrum to these events. However, Eibl et al. state that each of the t_{post} times follow their own log-normal distributed, while all of the t_{pre} times follow the same log-normal distribution [7]. The distribution of the t_{intra} times are also invariant, but are not further analysed or classified.

One has to be careful, however, when trying to evaluate how these distributions map to

eruption type	t_{post}	t_{pre}	t_{intra}
single	222 ± 54 s	252 ± 90 s	-
double	372 ± 78 s	234 ± 72 s	15.6 ± 4.5 s
triple	528 ± 174 s	234 ± 66 s	17.9 ± 5.5 s
quadruple	670 ± 174 s	222 ± 60 s	18.5 ± 5.8 s

Table 1: Mean preeruption, posteruption and intraeruption times. The uncertainty interval is given by one standard deviation of the underlying data set [7]. For the means and standard deviations of the fitted log-normal distributions, for single, double and triple eruption events, see [7].

the obtained spectra. One minor difficulty is missing data on the times between events of n -tuple eruptions, since t_{intra} only considers distance between the starting and ending times. A major difficulty is that the methods consider a number of time-distances, which is much higher, or in the case of the much CCM lower (namely 2, 836² and for the CCM 2, 836), than the number of time-distances one would obtain from adding all occurrences of the characteristic times (leading to 5, 115 events ($\approx 0.06\%$ and 180.36% of the considered data respectively)). Also every method varies in the way they obtain the possible set of frequencies, further complicating this issue.

Therefore, a hypothesis of how these distributions would map to a spectrum, has to be made for each method individually. This detailed testing is beyond the scope of this work. Instead, I will limit my analysis to brief descriptions of the spectra and how well these different characteristic time-scales are observable.

In the following subsection I will start this analysis with the CCM.

4.2. Spectral Analysis using the CCM

The CCM-generated ACF and PSE can be seen in fig. 23. Since I want to focus on the analysis of the spectra and keep the analysis of the ACF brief, I decided to show the ACF over the entire given time-lag domain, to highlight its overall behaviour.

The ACF shows behaviour which can be expected with the knowledge of the underlying definition. Firstly, it is 1 for $\tau = 0$ and has two symmetric negative minima in the neighbourhood around 0 (at -88.7 s and 88.7 s). The absence of either of these characteristic features, ($R(0) = 1$ and the negative symmetric minima near 0) would have indicated an erroneous calculation. The next obvious characteristic of this ACF is its asymmetry w.r.t. the τ -axis. This is a behaviour we already saw in the analytical examples and can be traced back to the same mechanism which causes the discontinuities. The issue with this asymmetry lies in the interpretation, since the classical explanation of correlation does not align with the correlation in the event-data case. In the classical case, this sparse negative correlation for any time-lag would indicate that the amplitude of the time-series is increasing almost everywhere. In the event-data case for the CCM, the sparse negativity indicates that there exist almost no time-lag for which the time-series is shifted by half a phase. This, in turn, indicates that the time-series is not well explained by a one-phase model, which is problematic for the CCM,

Figure 23: Spectrum and ACF obtained from the geyser data discussed in (subsec. 4.1) using the CCM. The spectrum is shown on the right, while the left shows the ACF. The ACF is shown over the duration given by the data. The inset window depicts the expected symmetric global minima around the time $\tau = 0$.

since it heavily depends on the average inter-event time.

The PSE on the right is shown in log-log-space for better visualisation. Here, one also sees behaviour expected from the given background. Firstly, a peak at 0.00473 Hz is visible, corresponding to a time-scale of ≈ 211.42 s. This is no surprise, since the average inter-event time for our subset is $\frac{604705.75665\text{s}}{2835} \approx 213.30\text{s}$. This time also corresponds to the posteruption time t_{post} of single eruption events and the preeruption time t_{pre} . Secondly, on the right side of the peak (towards higher frequencies), the spectrum decays faster compared to the left side. High frequencies are not as pronounced, with the exception of a peak at 0.012679 Hz (≈ 78.87 s), which is very prominent in his neighbourhood. Calculating a moving z-score with a window-size of 5,000 at this position yields ≈ 9.3 , which is higher than the moving z-score of the global maximum (≈ 9.19), underlying the significance of the former. However, this peak can not be attributed to one of the mechanisms described above (tab. 1). The remainder of the spectrum shows no additional prominent peaks in this preliminary analysis. A more detailed investigation is required, using a method that accounts for the varying density of the values more effectively than the moving z-score analysis. The comparatively low amplitudes and visually insignificant peaks suggests an inability to reliably detect frequencies corresponding to times shorter than the average inter-event interval.

The most significant peak on the left side of the maximum, which can not be attributed to the characteristic time of the maximum, is at a frequency of 0.00165431 Hz (604.48 s). This result is unexpected since this peak can be attributed to triple or quadruple eruption events (tab. 1), which are expected to be only 5% of the data.

After I discussed the CCM, let us turn our attention to the OM, in the next subsection.

Figure 24: Spectrum and ACF obtained from the geyser data using the OM. The spectrum is shown on the right, while the left shows the ACF. The ACF is shown over the duration given by the data. The inset window depicts the expected symmetric global minima around the time $\tau = 0$.

4.3. Spectral Analysis using the OM

When analysing the ACF generated by the OM (fig. 24), one can immediately spot a significant difference. While the behaviour around $\tau \approx 0$ is similar, again indicating the validity of the calculation, the behaviour w.r.t. the time-lag axis is not. This could be an indication that this asymmetric behaviour of the CCM is indeed due to the mechanism which causes the discontinuities. The OM is, of course, also not symmetric in a strict sense (since that would violate the definition of the ACF as a function), but one can clearly see that negative correlation is not as sparse. This difference in the ACF of the CCM and the OM might have an impact on the usefulness of the ACFs for methods, which are built on the analysis of the ACF. Keeping the analysis of the ACF brief, I will now focus on the PSE.

The PSE of the OM also has similarities to the PSE generated by the CCM, but they do have notable differences. The obvious similarity is their shared global maximum, at 0.00473 Hz (corresponding to a time of 211.42 s). This, as described above, corresponds to the average inter-event time and is explainable with the t_{post} time for singular events and the t_{pre} times. The further analysis on the right of the global maximum is complicated by the harmonics of the maximum and its neighbourhood. Since we know that a gaussian cut-off is used for the OM, I assume that this curve is attributable to the influence of the cut-off. I expect that this is a mechanism which is similar to that of the influence of the sampling function on the spectrum of continuous data, which was discussed together with the sampling theorem above subsec. 2.2.

However, another group of peaks at $f \approx 0.01$ (100 s) Hz can be distinguished. This group likely corresponds to the peak previously discovered in the CCM spectrum, since they have a short temporal distance and both exhibit side maxima. As already mentioned, both peaks can not be attributed to the known time-scales (tab. 1).

On the left side of the spectrum a significant peak at 0.00165372 Hz (604.70 s) can be found.

This peak, again, was already found in the CCM spectrum. As already discussed, this peak corresponds to triple or quadruple eruption events.

A significant difference to the CCM spectrum is the resolution of peaks for high frequencies $f > 0.17$ Hz. Multiple groups of peaks are resolved, namely at $f_1 \approx 0.18$ Hz (5.5' s), $f_2 \approx 0.25$ Hz (4 s), $f_3 \approx 0.35$ Hz (2.86 s), $f_4 \approx 0.5$ Hz (2 s) and $f_5 \approx 0.8$ Hz (1.25 s). These times can not be attributed to one of the given characteristic times either (tab. 1). They could be explained with inter-eruption times of triple or quadruple eruption events, further suggesting that this subset of the data contains a unexpected amount of triple or quadruple eruption events.

This brief analysis illustrates the expected advantages and disadvantages of the OM; when compared to the CCM, the spectrum has a much clearer structure, due to the gaussian cut-off. In contrast to the CCM, the ACF is also symmetric, which might be advantageous for further applications. One should be careful when interpreting the difference between the ACFs however, because a direct comparison implies that correlation is a well-established concept in the analysis of event-based time-series, which is not the case. Therefore, an interpretation of the correlation coefficients (and therefore that of the ACF) can only be consistently given from the underlying definitions of the measures, which are inherently different.

The gaussian cut-off is not only advantageous for the spectral analysis, however. The harmonics of the cut-off render a large interval in frequency space difficult to analyse.

After the spectral analysis with the correlation-based methods, let us focus on the series expansion approaches in the following subsections, starting with the AvIT-Expansion.

4.4. Spectral Analysis using the AvIT-Expansion

In this part, I discuss the results obtained with the AvIT-Expansion. While the time-series of the expansion function does not offer many insights into the matter, the spectrum helps to better understand how the AvIT-Expansion works in this case. In fig. 25, the finite-size effect is clearly visible on the left side of the spectrum. The overall amplitude increase for frequencies $f < 10^{-4}$ Hz, is solely attributable to the finite-size effect. This leaves a large proportion of the spectrum difficult to analyse. Therefore, I will limited the analysis to frequencies above 10^{-4} Hz (fig. 26).

For this small interval and resolution, it is still possible to extract meaningful information, due to the intrinsic meaning of the a_k . First of all, the large amplitude for a_1 (corresponding to 213.30 s, first peak from the right) indicates that the process is governed by an underlying dynamic that happens mostly between consecutive events. This fits to the large number of singular eruption events in the dataset and the preeruption times t_{pre} . Following the logic of the underlying model and the distribution of multiple events, one would have expected that the amplitudes of the coefficients decay more or less smoothly. However, after a_3 (corresponding to 639.9 s, i.e. t_{post} of quadruple eruption events) reaches a minimum, the coefficients increase again. The following local maxima are a_5 (corresponding to a time-scale of ≈ 18 min), a_9 (corresponding to a time-scale of ≈ 32 min), a_{14} (corresponding to a time-scale of ≈ 50 min), a_{20} (corresponding to a time-scale of ≈ 1.2 h) and a_{34} (corresponding to a time-scale of ≈ 2 h). Since these are not attributable to the finite-size effect, the AvIT-Expansion suggests far longer underlying dynamics, than present in the model.

Figure 25: Spectrum and AvIT-Expansion function obtained from the geyser data. The spectrum is shown on the right, while the left shows the expansion function. This function is shown over the duration of the given data (one week). The function was calculated by thresholding the time-scales, i.e. only considering those expansion coefficients which correspond to time-scales below the threshold of 5 hours.

Figure 26: Spectrum obtained from the AvIT-Expansion for frequencies above 10^{-4} Hz. Due to the low resolution in the frequency space, this plot was done with impulses.

Figure 27: Spectrum and LF obtained from the geyser data. The spectrum is shown on the right, while the left shows the LF. The LF is shown over the duration of the given data (one week), this choice of course is arbitrary and could be made differently.

One should be careful before jumping to any conclusions, though, since the amplitudes of these processes are a magnitude lower than the results from the LE. Without going further into the results of the LE just now (I will discuss those in the next subsection), this is a clear indicator that these long-term effects have only a minor contribution to the overall dynamic. This small analysis highlights the difficulties and disadvantages of the AvIT-Expansion, which we already discussed above. The first being the finite-size effect, while the second is the resolution for high frequencies in frequency space.

While the finite-size effect is an issue which should not be underestimated in its impact on the results, the resolution problem is not necessarily so problematic when the AvIT-Expansion is used to analyse data with a different background. One could imagine that if an underlying dynamic is spanned over multiple events, the AvIT-Expansion is a suitable tool to discover this dynamic.

4.5. Spectral Analysis using the LANGE-Expansion

In the end, I show the results obtained by the LANGE-Expansion (fig. 27). The LF's behaviour is difficult to grasp directly on the depicted time-domain. The complex behaviour deserves a detailed analysis (on a smaller time-scale than depicted in the plot), which is beyond the scope of this work. Instead, I want to focus on the spectrum.

The spectrum on the right depicts intriguing results. It shows a clear global maximum at $f_{\max} \approx 0.004738$ Hz, indicating a process with a characteristic time of 211,06 s. This, of course, corresponds to the t_{pre} time and the t_{post} times for single eruption events. The spectrum decays for lower frequencies, but local maxima are still clearly visible. This decline starts at a frequency of $\approx 0.0043'$ Hz (230.79 s).

A moving z-score analysis, with window size 1000, of the spectrum reveals significant peaks for low frequencies at ≈ 0.002111 Hz (473.69 s), ≈ 0.001625 Hz (615.55 s) and ≈ 0.001302 Hz (768 s). These peaks can be understood with the t_{post} times of the double, triple and

Figure 28: Spectrum (upper half) obtained from the LANGE-Expansion with z-Score analysis. The significant peaks (those above the threshold in the lower plot) are marked with red dots. The z-Scores of the peaks in shown in the lower plot. A further analysis should be done by using methods that account better for the varying density of the values than the moving z-Score.

quadruple eruption events.

The analysis shows many more significant peaks for the pther of the spectrum. We will focus on two of them. The first is the peak with the highest significants at $f_1 \approx 0.01364$ Hz (74.76 s) and the second is the peak with the second highest significants at $f_2 \approx 0.1576'$ Hz (6.342 s). f_1 corresponds to the peaks which were already found in the spectrum of the CCM and OM. Those were not explainable with the given charateristic times, indicating a unknown dynamic. f_2 could be attributed to the times between eruptions of triple and quadruple eruption events, as we already discussed for the OM. With the frequencies recovered in the lower end of this spectrum, this again hints at more triple or quadruple events than expected. A more detailed analysis is beyond the scope of this work, however, the further analysis of this spectrum, might be a fertail ground for the understanding of the geyser's dynamics.

With this example, one can clearly see the advantages and power of the LE. For example, it was possible to detect a frequency which is currently not present in the underlying model. Due to the good resolution in frequency space, one can extract reliable information over the entire spectrum. This clearly separates the LE from the other methods developed in this work. For further analysis, one could also calculate the spectrum for other subsets of the data to analyse the time-evolution of the spectrum and therefore non-linear aspects of the time-evolution of the underlying phases.

5. Discussion

In this chapter I discuss and summarize the most relevant results from the previous chapters in depth.

I will start with the Cosine-Correlation-Measure (**CCM**) (subsec. 3.1). This method was derived from the intuition on how a correlation coefficient for two event-based time-series (T_M and \mathcal{T}_n) could be introduced. In short, it firstly calculates unique pairs of events, by ensuring that the events of these pairs are uniquely paired with their closest temporal neighbour from the other time-series. It then converts this temporal distance into an angle and averages over the cosine of this angle, leading to a correlation coefficient, when normalised properly.

The CCM can then be used to calculate an autocorrelation function (**ACF**). This, in turn, can then be Fourier-transformed, which leads to a spectrum.

We saw that this method is a suitable way to analytically form an understanding on the correlation between event-based time-series, but, due to the way pairs are obtained, it is numerically more difficult to implement when compared to the other methods. In the analytical examples, I showed that the CCM is not able to reconstruct the entire spectrum of a time-series reliably, due to the choice of the time-scale in the calculation of the angle. Instead the results are reliable for times larger than the average inter-event time. These results were echoed in the analysis of the real-world data. Here only one frequency corresponding to a time below the average inter-event time could be extracted reliably.

Trying to resolve some issues from the CCM (namely the discontinuities of the ACF and the numerical implementation), the second method, the Overlap-Measure (**OM**), was implemented in the next chapter (subsec. 3.2). Here, one also calculates a correlation coefficient, which then can be used to calculate the ACF and a spectrum. There are major differences to the CCM, though. The OM considers all pairs of values and uses a weighted sum and difference of the time-values to calculate angles. The cosines of these sums and differences are multiplied with a gaussian cut-off function, which considers the weighted temporal distance between events. The weights of the cut-off are the average inter-event times of the respective time-series.

This difference in the definition (compared to the CCM) leads to a simpler numerical implementation, but sacrifices the simple analytical calculation in turn. The normalisation of the correlation is also computationally more expensive, since it requires the unnormalised coefficient to be calculated on the two time-series individually. In the end, the maximum of these two values is chosen for the normalisation. In its entirety, for two time-series T_m and \mathcal{T}_n , this leads to the calculation of a sum over an $n \times m$ matrix (unnormalised correlation coefficient), an $n \times n$ matrix (first possible normalisation) and a $m \times m$ matrix (second possible normalisation). While the CCM only needed to calculate the distance of $\min\{n, m\}$ pairs, since its normalisation has a simple analytical expression.

Apart from computational differences, their results on the geyser data also differed, with the OM's PSE suffering from the higher harmonics of the gaussian cut-off. However, we were able to extract some spectral information, with more information being recovered on the higher end of the spectrum. This is a big advantage compared to the CCM. The ACF of both methods also differed a lot, with the CCM's showing sparse negative correlation and the OM's

a higher symmetry.

Due to the prominent role of the average inter-event time in both methods, I focussed on another approach, namely a series expansion Ansatz, in the next chapters. The first of these series expansion methods is the Average Inter-Event Time-Expansion (**AvIT-Expansion**) (subsec. 3.3).

Here I wanted to solve the dependence on the chosen time-scales, by expanding the time-series with harmonic functions. Whose frequencies are given as of multiples of the average inter-event time. This approach converts an event-based time-series into a continuous time-series and produces a spectrum in the process. The definition of an expansion coefficient a_k also adds another intuitive layer to the spectrum of an event-based time-series, with a high value for a_k corresponding to an underlying process that reoccurs every $k - 1$ events.

The main issues of the AvIT-Expansion are the finite-size effect (fig. 12), which is a mathematical artifact resulting from the finite-size of the given data and the resolution for high frequencies, namely those corresponding to time-scales below the average inter-event time.

When applying the AvIT-Expansion on the geyser data (subsec. 4.4), we saw that these two issues made the analysis difficult, but one can adjust to them and still get some insights on the underlying process.

The last method I developed was another series expansion approach. In contrast to the AvIT-Expansion, it sampled equally through the frequency space of a given event-based time-series, in accordance with the sampling theorem. Since this a more general method than the AvIT-Expansion, but still a linear (phase) approximation in time, I called it the Linear phase-Approximation of Non-trivial General Event-data-Expansion (**LANGE-Expansion**) (subsec. 3.4).

Its series expansion (**LE**) and expansion function (**LF**) are obtained in a similar manner to those of the AvIT-Expansion, with the key difference that a greater effort was put into the mathematical foundation to avoid artifacts such as the finite-size effect.

Although this method is computationally more expensive than the AvIT-Expansion, its results prove to reflect a more complete picture of the spectrum of a time-series. Also, the analytical foundation helps to analytically derive further analysis tools, such as the ACF.

When using the LE to analyse the geyser data (subsec. 4.5), we saw that the LE was able to recover significant frequencies well below those corresponding to the average inter-event time. The peaks of the data were also more profound than in the CCM data and the spectrum did not suffer from structural difficulties like the spectra from the OM and AvIT.

With 3 of our 4 methods I also extracted a significant time-scale of $t \approx 70 - 100$ s, which is not present in the current model of the geyser.

After this discussion, in the last chapter of this work, I conclude the main findings of this master thesis.

6. Conclusion

In this master thesis, I investigated the subject of the spectral analysis of event-based time-series, by proposing four different methods to calculate such spectra. In the first part of this work, I derived these methods mathematically and tested them on analytical examples. The second part showed the results obtained by these methods, when applied to a real-world example, namely data from the Strokkur geyser in Iceland [7]. Now I will briefly go through these four methods and conclude their advantages and disadvantages.

The strength of the first method, the Cosine-Correlation-Measure (CCM), lies in the calculation of a correlation coefficient and its analytical simplicity. Compared to the OM, it also requires fewer computational resources. However, since it still has a the high computational expense and it is unable to recover the entire spectrum (namely the high-end) reliably, the use for spectral analysis is limited.

For the second method, the Overlap-Measure (OM), I conclude that it is also better used to determine correlation between two time-series, since the PSE suffers from higher harmonics of its cut-off function. However, it is able to recover information on the high-end of the spectrum and its ACF might prove to be useful for further development of analysis methods. The third method, the Average Inter-Event Time-Expansion (AvIT-Expansion), is best used for long data sets (due to the low computational time), whose physical background hints at long-cycle processes or to deliberately find such long-cycle processes in the given data. With the low resolution for high frequencies and the finite-size effect, the AvIT-Expansion's spectral information requires a good understanding of the underlying definitions.

The last method, the Linear phase-Approximation of Non-trivial General Event-data-Expansion (LANGE-Expansion), prove to be the most reliable in the analytic tests and the analysis of the real-world data. The analytical foundation simplifies the analysis and offeres a fertial ground for further investigation. It also requires less computational expense compared to the CCM and OM.

To conclude, the first two methods (CCM and OM) have their strengths in the calculation of correlation between time-series, the last two methods (AvIT and LANGE-Expansion) are suitable tools to analyse the spectrum of an event-based time-series. While the AvIT-Expansions focuses on the low-end of frequencies, the LANGE-Expansion offers a broad overview of the entire spectrum.

For further research, these methods should undergo detailed testing, especially hypothesis testing. Also sensitive testings (e.g. w.r.t. to data set length and noise-level.) should be conducted on these methods. Using these methods on other data might also prove insightful. To reach their full potential, the methods could be investigated as part of other analysis methods. The use of their generated continuous representation of event-data (ACFs and the respective expansion-functions) for continuous time-series analysis methods could be investigated. A research into backtransformations from the LANGE and AvIT-Expansion to event-data might be fruitful.

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A. Mathematical Proofs

A.1. Proof of the Coinciding of Time-Resolved and Simple Mean for a Simple Time-Series

It is to show that:

$$\mu(\chi_m) = \gamma(\chi_m), \forall \chi_m \text{ with } t_i - t_{i-1} = \Delta t \forall i \in \{2, \dots, m\} \quad (207)$$

with the definition of the mean $\mu(\chi_m)$ eq.(eq. 10) and the time-resolved mean $\gamma(\chi_m)$ eq.(eq. 17).

$$\gamma(\chi_m) = \frac{1}{t_m - t_1} \left(\sum_{i=2}^{m-1} \frac{x_i}{2} (t_{i+1} - t_{i-1}) + \frac{x_1}{2} (t_2 - t_1) + \frac{x_m}{2} (t_m - t_{m-1}) \right) \quad (208)$$

$$= \frac{1}{m\Delta t} \left(\sum_{i=2}^{m-1} \frac{x_i}{2} (t_{i+1} + t_i - t_i - t_{i-1}) + x_1\Delta t + x_m\Delta t \right) \quad (209)$$

$$= \frac{1}{m\Delta t} \left(\sum_{i=2}^{m-1} \frac{x_i}{2} 2\Delta t + x_1\Delta t + x_m\Delta t \right) \quad (210)$$

$$= \frac{\Delta t}{m\Delta t} \left(\sum_{i=2}^{m-1} x_i + x_1 + x_m \right) \quad (211)$$

$$= \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m x_i \quad (212)$$

$$= \mu(\chi_m). \quad (213)$$

A.2. Proof of the Coinciding of Time-Resolved and Simple Standard-Deviation for a Simple Time-Series

It is to show that:

$$\text{std}(\chi_m) = \text{std}_{\text{time}}(\chi_m), \forall \chi_m \text{ with } t_i - t_{i-1} = \Delta t \forall i \in \{2, \dots, m\} \quad (214)$$

with the definition of the standard deviation $\text{std}(\chi_m)$ eq.(eq. 19) and the time-resolved standard deviation $\text{std}_{\text{time}}(\chi_m)$ eq.(eq. 21).

$$\text{std}_{\text{time}}(\chi_m) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{t_m - t_1} \sum_{i=2}^{m-1} \frac{(x_i - \gamma)^2}{2} (t_{i+1} - t_{i-1}) + (x_1 - \gamma)^2 (t_2 - t_1) + (x_m - \gamma)^2 (t_m - t_{m-1})} \quad (215)$$

$$= \sqrt{\frac{1}{m\Delta t} \sum_{i=2}^{m-1} \frac{(x_i - \gamma)^2}{2} 2\Delta t + (x_1 - \gamma)^2 \Delta t + (x_m - \gamma)^2 \Delta t} \quad (216)$$

$$= \sqrt{\frac{\Delta t}{m\Delta t} \sum_{i=2}^{m-1} (x_i - \gamma)^2 + (x_1 - \gamma)^2 + (x_m - \gamma)^2} \quad (217)$$

$$= \sqrt{\frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^{m-1} (x_i - \gamma)^2} \quad (218)$$

$$= \text{std}(\chi_m). \quad (219)$$

A.3. Proof of the Broadening of the Spectra due to Gaussian Cut-Off

Let \mathcal{F} denote the one-dimensional Fourier transformation, defined as an operation mapping from and to the space of Square-integrable $L^2(\mathbb{R})$ functions.

$$\mathcal{F} : \mathcal{L}^2(\mathbb{R}) \rightarrow \mathcal{L}^2(\mathbb{R}) \quad (220)$$

$$f(t) \mapsto \hat{f}(\omega) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{\mathbb{R}} f(x) e^{-i\omega t} dt, \quad (221)$$

with i being the imaginary unit. The gaussian function is the Eigenfunction of the Fourier transformation to the Eigenvalue 1, i.e.

$$\mathcal{F} \left(e^{-\frac{t^2}{2}} \right) (\omega) = e^{-\frac{\omega^2}{2}}. \quad (222)$$

I want to show that the product of a periodic function $g(t)$ (representable with its Fourier series as a sum of sine and cosine terms) and a gaussian cut-off leads to a broadening of the spectrum of the periodic function. In the first step, I will use that the Fourier transformation of a product of functions is just the convolution of the Fourier transformations:

$$\mathcal{F} \left(g(t) e^{-\frac{t^2}{2\Delta t^2}} \right) = \mathcal{F}(g(t)) * \mathcal{F} \left(e^{-\frac{t^2}{2\Delta t^2}} \right). \quad (223)$$

Now I will use that the Fourier transformation is linear, i.e. a Fourier transformation of the sum is just the sum of the Fourier transformations, that the Fourier transformation of cosine

and sine functions are sums of δ -functions and the definition of the Fourier transformation (eq. 220), i.e.

$$\mathcal{F}(g(t)) * \mathcal{F}\left(e^{-\frac{t^2}{2\Delta t^2}}\right) = \sum_k \delta(\omega - \omega_k) * \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{\mathbb{R}} e^{-\frac{t^2}{2\Delta t^2}} e^{-i\omega t} dt \quad (224)$$

$$= \sum_k \delta(\omega - \omega_k) * \int_{\mathbb{R}} e^{-\frac{\tilde{t}^2}{2}} e^{-i\omega \tilde{t} \Delta t} \Delta t d\tilde{t} \quad (225)$$

$$= \sum_k \delta(\omega - \omega_k) * \int_{\mathbb{R}} e^{-\frac{\tilde{t}^2}{2}} e^{-i\tilde{\omega} \tilde{t}} \Delta t d\tilde{t} \quad (226)$$

$$= \sum_k \delta(\omega - \omega_k) * \mathcal{F}\left(e^{-\frac{\tilde{t}^2}{2}}\right)(\tilde{\omega}) \Delta t \quad (227)$$

$$= \sum_k \delta(\omega - \omega_k) * e^{-\frac{\tilde{\omega}^2}{2}} \Delta t \quad (228)$$

$$= \sum_k \delta(\omega - \omega_k) * e^{-\frac{\Delta t^2 \omega^2}{2}} \Delta t \quad (229)$$

$$= \int_{\mathbb{R}} \sum_k \delta(\omega - \omega_k) e^{-\frac{\Delta t^2 (\omega - y)^2}{2}} \Delta t dy \quad (230)$$

$$= \sum_k e^{-\frac{\Delta t^2 (\omega - \omega_k)^2}{2}} \Delta t \quad (231)$$

$$= \frac{1}{\Delta \omega} \sum_k e^{-\frac{(\omega - \omega_k)^2}{2\Delta \omega^2}}. \quad (232)$$

$$(233)$$

Which proves exactly what I wanted to show, i.e. the resulting spectra are just Gaussian functions at the positions of the original spectrum $\hat{g}(\omega)$ with a broadening of $\Delta \omega = \frac{1}{\Delta t}$. Here, one can easily understand what happens with the spectrum, if the cutoff is increased or decreased.

A.4. Proof of the Connection between the Harmonic Mean and the Average Event-Frequency

The **harmonic mean** μ_{harmonic} of any sequence $(u_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, m\}} \in \mathcal{S}_m(\mathbb{R})$ can be defined as the following map

$$\mu_{\text{harmonic}} : \mathcal{S}_m(\mathbb{R}) \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \quad (234)$$

$$(u_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, m\}} \mapsto \frac{m}{\sum_{i=1}^m \frac{1}{u_i}}. \quad (235)$$

Now, to proof that the inverse harmonic mean of the sequence of inter-event times is the average event-frequency, we have to first consider the sequence of inter-event times $(\delta t_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, m-1\}} \in$

$\mathcal{S}_{m-1}(\mathbb{R}^+)$, which is obtained from an event-based time-series T_m with the following map

$$\delta t_{T_m} : \mathcal{S}_m^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_{m-1}(\mathbb{R}^+) \quad (236)$$

$$T_m \mapsto (\delta t_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, m-1\}} = (t_{k+1} - t_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, m-1\}}. \quad (237)$$

Using now the definition of μ_{harmonic} on this sequence leads us straightforwardly to what we wanted to show:

$$\mu_{\text{harmonic}}((\delta t_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, m-1\}}) = \frac{m-1}{\sum_{i=1}^{m-1} \frac{1}{\delta t_i}} \quad (238)$$

$$= \frac{m-1}{\sum_{i=1}^{m-1} \frac{1}{t_{i+1} - t_i}} \quad (239)$$

$$= \frac{1}{\delta f}. \quad (240)$$

The set $(\Delta f_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, m-1\}}$ could therefore be defined with the following map:

$$\Delta f_{t_m} : \mathcal{S}_m^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_{m-1}^<(\mathbb{R}^+) \quad (241)$$

$$T_m \mapsto (\Delta f_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, m-1\}} = \left(\frac{k}{\mu_{\text{harmonic}}((\delta t_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, m-1\}})} \right)_{k \in \{1, \dots, m-1\}}. \quad (242)$$

It is also clear that the definition of the time-scales of the average inter-event time is just the arithmetic (simple) mean μ (see eq. 40) of the inter-event time-sequence:

$$\mu((\delta t_k)_{k \in \{1, \dots, m-1\}}) = \frac{1}{m-1} \sum_{k=1}^{m-1} \delta t_k \quad (243)$$

$$= \frac{1}{m-1} (t_k - t_{k-1} + t_{k+1} - t_{k+2} + \dots + t_3 - t_2 + t_2 - t_1) \quad (244)$$

$$= \frac{1}{m-1} (t_k - t_1) = \Delta t_1. \quad (245)$$

A.5. Proof of the Inner Product Space $(\mathcal{P}, \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle)$

To proof that $(\mathcal{P}, \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle)$ is a inner product space, one has to show that for $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ on $\mathcal{P}([t_1, t_m], \mathbb{R}) \times \mathcal{P}([t_m, t_1], \mathbb{R})$ the following conditions hold $\forall p, q, r \in \mathcal{P}([t_m, t_1], \mathbb{R}), \alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{R}$ ([16]):

$$\langle p, p \rangle \in \mathbb{R} \wedge \langle p, p \rangle \geq 0, \quad (246)$$

$$\langle p, p \rangle = 0 \Leftrightarrow p = 0, \quad (247)$$

$$\langle \alpha p + \beta q, p \rangle = \alpha \langle p, p \rangle + \beta \langle q, p \rangle, \quad (248)$$

$$\langle p, q \rangle = \langle q, p \rangle. \quad (249)$$

First let us emphasize again that all functions $p \in \mathcal{P}([t_1, t_m], \mathbb{R})$ are integrable and square-integrable, so

$$\int_{t_1}^{t_m} p(t)dt \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (250)$$

$$\int_{t_1}^{t_m} p^2(t)dt \in \mathbb{R}. \quad (251)$$

The first condition therefore holds true per definition, since:

$$\langle p, p \rangle = \int_{t_1}^{t_m} p^2(t)dt. \quad (252)$$

And since these functions are mapping on \mathbb{R} follows that $p^2(t) \geq 0 \forall t \in \mathbb{R}$ and therefore follows $\langle p, p \rangle \geq 0$.

For the second function, we first have to define what $p = 0$ actually suppose to mean. The naive approach would be to say that $p = 0$ is equivalent to $p(t) = 0 \forall t \in [t_1, t_m]$. With this choice, one would run into problems with functions $p(t)$, which are 0 *almost everywhere* (non-zero only for values of t , which are part of a set with measure zero), e.g. the Dirichlet function $d(t)$ [16]:

$$d(t) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } t \in \mathbb{Q} \cap [t_1, t_m], \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases}. \quad (253)$$

The problem now is that $\int_{t_1}^{t_m} d(t)dt = 0$ and therefore $\langle d, d \rangle = 0$, violating the second condition, since the Dirichlet function is not the zero function. To avoid this mathematical problem, one typically defines the elements of the space $\mathcal{P}([t_1, t_m], \mathbb{R})$ not as integrable and square-integrable functions, but as equivalence classes of integrable and square-integrable functions with the underlying equivalence relation

$$f \sim g \text{ if and only if } f = g \text{ almost everywhere.} \quad (254)$$

The nuances, details and proofs of all this are explained in various textbooks, e.g. [16]. Like Castillo, I will drop this technicality in the notation for simplicity and stick to talking about functions $p(t) \in \mathcal{P}([t_1, t_m], \mathbb{R})$, although I implicitly mean the equivalence classes of those functions [16].

The last two conditions are easily shown with the linearity of the integral:

$$\langle \alpha p + \beta q, p \rangle = \int_{t_1}^{t_m} (\alpha p(t) + \beta q(t))p(t)dt \quad (255)$$

$$= \alpha \int_{t_1}^{t_m} p(t)p(t)dt + \beta \int_{t_1}^{t_m} q(t)p(t)dt \quad (256)$$

$$= \alpha \langle p, p \rangle + \beta \langle q, p \rangle. \quad (257)$$

And

$$\langle p, q \rangle = \int_{t_1}^{t_m} p(t)q(t)dt \quad (258)$$

$$= \int_{t_1}^{t_m} q(t)p(t)dt \quad (259)$$

$$= \langle q, p \rangle. \quad (260)$$

Thus proving that $(\mathcal{P}, \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle)$ is an inner product space.

A.6. Proof of the Non-Orthogonality of the AvIT-Expansion

To show that the expansion functions of the AvIT-Expansion are non-orthogonal w.r.t. the inner product I defined above (eq. 162) and the space $L_2([t_1, t_m], \mathbb{R}) \cap L_1([t_1, t_m], \mathbb{R})$, I will search for two basis functions $f(t), g(t)$ of the AvIT-Expansion, so that $|\langle f, g \rangle| > 0$. The space $L_2([t_1, t_m], \mathbb{R}) \cap L_1([t_1, t_m], \mathbb{R})$ is an inner product space with the inner product, with the same proof as the space $\mathcal{P}([t_1, t_m], \mathbb{R})$, since the periodicity of the functions had no effect on the proof subsec. A.5.

We will choose our first function as $f(t) = \cos\left(\frac{2\pi(t-t_1)(m-1)}{2(t_m-t_1)}\right)$ corresponding to $k = 2$ and to the expansion coefficient a_2 . The second function will be $g(t) = \cos\left(\frac{2\pi(t-t_1)(m-1)}{4(t_m-t_1)}\right)$ corresponding to a_4 . In the following, I will prove that their inner product is non-zero:

$$\langle f, g \rangle = \int_{t_1}^{t_m} \cos\left(\frac{2\pi(t-t_1)(m-1)}{2(t_m-t_1)}\right) \cos\left(\frac{2\pi(t-t_1)(m-1)}{4(t_m-t_1)}\right) dt \quad (261)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \left(\int_{t_1}^{t_m} \cos\left(\frac{2\pi(t-t_1)(m-1)}{(t_m-t_1)}\left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4}\right)\right) dt + \int_{t_1}^{t_m} \cos\left(\frac{2\pi(t-t_1)(m-1)}{(t_m-t_1)}\left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{4}\right)\right) dt \right) \quad (262)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \left(\int_{t_1}^{t_m} \cos\left(\frac{3\pi(t-t_1)(m-1)}{4(t_m-t_1)}\right) dt + \int_{t_1}^{t_m} \cos\left(\frac{\pi(t-t_1)(m-1)}{2(t_m-t_1)}\right) dt \right) \quad (263)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \left(\left[\frac{4(t_m-t_1)}{3\pi(m-1)} \sin\left(\frac{3\pi(t-t_1)(m-1)}{4(t_m-t_1)}\right) \right]_{t_1}^{t_m} + \left[\frac{2(t_m-t_1)}{\pi(m-1)} \sin\left(\frac{\pi(t-t_1)(m-1)}{2(t_m-t_1)}\right) \right]_{t_1}^{t_m} \right) \quad (264)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{4(t_m-t_1)}{3\pi(m-1)} \sin\left(\frac{3\pi(m-1)}{4}\right) + \frac{2(t_m-t_1)}{\pi(m-1)} \sin\left(\frac{\pi(m-1)}{2}\right) \right) \quad (265)$$

$$= (-1)^m \frac{1}{2} \frac{4(t_m-t_1)}{3\pi(m-1)} \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} \quad (266)$$

$$= (-1)^m \frac{\sqrt{2}(t_m-t_1)}{3\pi(m-1)} \quad (267)$$

$$\neq 0. \quad (268)$$

A.7. Proof of the Scalar Product of two LFs

Consider two LFs $l_{T_m}, l_{\mathcal{T}_n} \in \mathcal{P}([t_1, t_m], \mathbb{R})$, derived from two different event-based time-series T_m and \mathcal{T}_n , which have the same duration, i.e. $t_m^{T_m} - t_1^{T_m} = t_n^{\mathcal{T}_n} - t_1^{\mathcal{T}_n}$. The overlap of their two LFs can be calculated straight-forward

$$\langle l_{T_m}, l_{\mathcal{T}_n} \rangle = \left\langle \sum_{k=1}^M \lambda_k^{T_m} c_k, \sum_{j=1}^{M'} \lambda_j^{\mathcal{T}_n} c_j \right\rangle \quad (269)$$

$$= \sum_{k=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^{M'} \lambda_k^{T_m} \lambda_j^{\mathcal{T}_n} \langle c_k, c_j \rangle \quad (270)$$

$$= \sum_{k=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^{M'} \lambda_k^{T_m} \lambda_j^{\mathcal{T}_n} \frac{t_m - t_1}{2} \delta_{kj} \quad (271)$$

$$= \frac{t_m - t_1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^{\min\{M, M'\}} \lambda_k^{T_m} \lambda_k^{\mathcal{T}_n}. \quad (272)$$

With the usage of the properties of the scalar product (subsec. A.5) and the result from the scalar product of the basis functions (eq. 185).

A.8. Proof of the ACF for a General LF

Before I start to work on this proof, I have to establish something else beforehand. In the following, I use the notation $s_j = \sin\left(\frac{2j\pi(t-t_1)}{t_m-t_1}\right)$. $\forall k, j \in \mathbb{N} k \neq j$:

$$\langle c_k, s_j \rangle = \int_{t_1}^{t_m} \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi(t-t_1)}{t_m-t_1}\right) \sin\left(\frac{2j\pi(t-t_1)}{t_m-t_1}\right) dt \quad (273)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \int_{t_1}^{t_m} \left[\sin\left(\frac{2(k-j)\pi(t-t_1)}{t_m-t_1}\right) + \sin\left(\frac{2(k+j)\pi(t-t_1)}{t_m-t_1}\right) \right] dt \quad (274)$$

$$= \frac{t_m - t_1}{4\pi(t-t_1)} \left[-\frac{1}{k-j} \left[\cos\left(\frac{2(k-j)\pi(t-t_1)}{t_m-t_1}\right) \right]_{t_1}^{t_m} - \frac{1}{k+j} \left[\cos\left(\frac{2(k+j)\pi(t-t_1)}{t_m-t_1}\right) \right]_{t_1}^{t_m} \right] \quad (275)$$

$$= \frac{t_m - t_1}{4\pi(t-t_1)} \left[-\frac{1}{k-j}(1-1) - \frac{1}{k+j}(1-1) \right] \quad (276)$$

$$= 0. \quad (277)$$

If $k, j \in \mathbb{N}$ $k = j$, one can just plug $k = j$ into the second row to obtain:

$$\langle c_k, s_k \rangle = \frac{1}{2} \int_{t_1}^{t_m} \left[0 + \sin\left(\frac{4\pi(t-t_1)}{t_m-t_1}\right) \right] dt \quad (278)$$

$$= -\frac{1}{2} \frac{t_m-t_1}{4\pi(t-t_1)} \left[\cos\left(\frac{4\pi(t-t_1)}{t_m-t_1}\right) \right]_{t_1}^{t_m} \quad (279)$$

$$= -\frac{1}{2} \frac{t_m-t_1}{4\pi(t-t_1)} (1-1) \quad (280)$$

$$= 0. \quad (281)$$

For the following proof I will also use the following well-known trigonometric identity $\cos(x+y) = \cos(x)\cos(y) - \sin(x)\sin(y)$ in this notation as $c_j(x+y) = c_j(x)c_j(y) - s_j(x)s_j(y)$. I will prove the result of the ACF by a straightforward calculation

$$R_{\ell_{T_m}}(\tau) = \frac{1}{|\langle \ell_{T_m}, \ell_{T_m} \rangle|} \langle \ell_{T_m}, \ell_{T_m}(t+\tau) \rangle \quad (282)$$

$$= \frac{2}{(t_m-t_1) \sum_{k=1}^M \lambda_k^2} \langle \ell_{T_m}, \sum_{j=1}^M \lambda_j c_j(t+\tau) \rangle \quad (283)$$

$$= \frac{2}{(t_m-t_1) \sum_{k=1}^M \lambda_k^2} \langle \ell_{T_m}, \sum_{j=1}^M \lambda_j (c_j(t)c_j(\tau) - s_j(t)s_j(\tau)) \rangle \quad (284)$$

$$= \frac{2}{(t_m-t_1) \sum_{k=1}^M \lambda_k^2} \sum_{j=1}^M \lambda_j \langle \sum_{k=1}^M \lambda_k c_k, (c_j c_j(\tau) - s_j s_j(\tau)) \rangle \quad (285)$$

$$= \frac{2}{(t_m-t_1) \sum_{k=1}^M \lambda_k^2} \sum_{k,j=1}^M \lambda_j \lambda_k (\langle c_k, c_j c_j(\tau) \rangle - \langle c_k, s_j s_j(\tau) \rangle) \quad (286)$$

$$= \frac{2}{(t_m-t_1) \sum_{k=1}^M \lambda_k^2} \sum_{k,j=1}^M \lambda_j \lambda_k (c_j(\tau) \langle c_k, c_j \rangle - s_j(\tau) \langle c_k, s_j \rangle) \quad (287)$$

$$= \frac{2}{(t_m-t_1) \sum_{k=1}^M \lambda_k^2} \sum_{k,j=1}^M \lambda_j \lambda_k (c_j(\tau) \frac{t_m-t_1}{2} \delta_{kj} - 0) \quad (288)$$

$$= \frac{\sum_{k=1}^M \lambda_k^2 c_k(\tau)}{\sum_{k=1}^M \lambda_k^2}. \quad (289)$$

Here I used the results from the proof prior (subsec. A.7) and the fact that $c_j(\tau)$ is independent from the integration variable t in the scalar product, which allows for $c_j(\tau)$ to be treated as a simple scalar and the usage of the linearity of the scalar product.

A.9. Proof of the Convergence of the LANGE-Expansion for Simple Periodic Time-Series

It is to show that:

$$\lambda_{m-1} = 1 \quad (290)$$

$$\lambda_k = \frac{1}{m^2}, \quad \forall k \neq m-1. \quad (291)$$

With

$$\lambda_k = \frac{1}{m} + \frac{2}{m^2} \sum_{l=1}^{m-1} (m-l) \cos\left(\frac{2kl\pi}{m-1}\right). \quad (292)$$

The first part of the proof is easy, for $k = m-1$ it just follows:

$$\lambda_{m-1} = \frac{1}{m} + \frac{2}{m^2} \sum_{l=1}^{m-1} (m-l) \cos\left(\frac{2l\pi(m-1)}{m-1}\right) \quad (293)$$

$$= \frac{1}{m} + \frac{2}{m^2} \sum_{l=1}^{m-1} (m-l) \cos(2l\pi) \quad (294)$$

$$= \frac{1}{m} + \frac{2}{m^2} \sum_{l=1}^{m-1} (m-l) \quad (295)$$

$$= \frac{1}{m} + \frac{2}{m^2} \left(m \sum_{l=1}^{m-1} 1 - \sum_{l=1}^{m-1} l \right) \quad (296)$$

$$= \frac{1}{m} + \frac{2}{m^2} \left(m(m-1) - \frac{m(m-1)}{2} \right) \quad (297)$$

$$= \frac{1}{m} + \frac{2}{m^2} \left(\frac{m(m-1)}{2} \right) \quad (298)$$

$$= 1. \quad (299)$$

With the knowledge of the small Gauss, $\sum_{k=1}^m k = \frac{m(m+1)}{2}$, and that $\cos(2\pi l) = 1$, since l is a integer number.

For the second part, I can simplify the proof a little bit before I dive into the calculation of the sum:

$$\lambda_k = \frac{1}{m} + \frac{2}{m^2} \sum_{l=1}^{m-1} (m-l) \cos\left(\frac{2kl\pi}{m-1}\right) \stackrel{!}{=} \frac{1}{m^2} \quad (300)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \sum_{l=1}^{m-1} (m-l) \cos\left(\frac{2kl\pi}{m-1}\right) \stackrel{!}{=} \frac{m-1}{2}. \quad (301)$$

With that, I start by using the real part of Euler's formula $\cos(x) = \frac{e^{ix} + e^{-ix}}{2}$:

$$\sum_{l=1}^{m-1} (m-l) \cos\left(\frac{2kl\pi}{m-1}\right) = \sum_{l=1}^{m-1} (m-l) \left(\frac{e^{\frac{2ikl\pi}{m-1}} + e^{-\frac{2ikl\pi}{m-1}}}{2} \right), \quad (302)$$

this has the obvious advantage that, once the sums are split, the geometric sum can be used,

$$= \frac{m}{2} \left(\sum_{l=1}^{m-1} e^{\frac{2ikl\pi}{m-1}} + \sum_{l=1}^{m-1} e^{\frac{-2ikl\pi}{m-1}} \right) - \frac{1}{2} \left(\sum_{l=1}^{m-1} l e^{\frac{2ikl\pi}{m-1}} + \sum_{l=1}^{m-1} l e^{\frac{-2ikl\pi}{m-1}} \right) \quad (303)$$

$$= \frac{m}{2} \left(\sum_{l=1}^{m-1} (e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}})^l + \sum_{l=1}^{m-1} (e^{\frac{-2ik\pi}{m-1}})^l \right) - \frac{1}{2} \left(\sum_{l=1}^{m-1} l (e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}})^l + \sum_{l=1}^{m-1} l (e^{\frac{-2ik\pi}{m-1}})^l \right). \quad (304)$$

The general geometric sum for $a \neq 1$ yields:

$$\sum_{k=j}^n a^k = \frac{a^{n+1} - a^j}{a - 1}. \quad (305)$$

Since, in the second term, the summation index is in the product with the exponential function, I do a little trick:

$$\sum_{k=j}^n k e^{bk} = \sum_{k=j}^n \frac{d}{db} e^{bk} \quad (306)$$

$$= \frac{d}{db} \sum_{k=j}^n e^{bk} \quad (307)$$

$$= \frac{d}{db} \frac{e^{b(n+1)} - e^{bj}}{e^b - 1} \quad (308)$$

$$= \frac{(n+1)e^{b(n+1)} - j e^{bj}}{e^b - 1} - \frac{(e^{b(n+1)} - e^{bj})e^b}{(e^b - 1)^2}. \quad (309)$$

Now I plug both (eq. 305) and (eq. 309) into (eq. 304), with $a = e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}}$ or $a = e^{\frac{-2ik\pi}{m-1}}$, for the other sum (eq. 309), $b = \frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}$ or $b = \frac{-2ik\pi}{m-1}$, and in both cases, $j = 1$. The condition $a \neq 1$ holds in both cases, since the case $k = m-1$ was treated above and here $k \neq m-1$. For the sake of visibility, I treat each term separately before combining them.

$$\sum_{l=1}^{m-1} (e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}})^l = \frac{e^{\frac{2ikm\pi}{m-1}} - e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}}}{e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}} - 1}, \quad (310)$$

$$\sum_{l=1}^{m-1} (e^{\frac{-2ik\pi}{m-1}})^l = \frac{e^{\frac{-2ikm\pi}{m-1}} - e^{\frac{-2ik\pi}{m-1}}}{e^{\frac{-2ik\pi}{m-1}} - 1}, \quad (311)$$

$$\sum_{l=1}^{m-1} l (e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}})^l = \frac{m e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}} - e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}}}{e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}} - 1} - \frac{(e^{\frac{2ikm\pi}{m-1}} - e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}}) e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}}}{(e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}} - 1)^2}, \quad (312)$$

$$\sum_{l=1}^{m-1} l (e^{\frac{-2ik\pi}{m-1}})^l = \frac{m e^{\frac{-2ik\pi}{m-1}} - e^{\frac{-2ik\pi}{m-1}}}{e^{\frac{-2ik\pi}{m-1}} - 1} - \frac{(e^{\frac{-2ikm\pi}{m-1}} - e^{\frac{-2ik\pi}{m-1}}) e^{\frac{-2ik\pi}{m-1}}}{(e^{\frac{-2ik\pi}{m-1}} - 1)^2}. \quad (313)$$

Now, with these (eq. 304) is:

$$= \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{me^{\frac{2ikm\pi}{m-1}} - me^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}}}{e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}} - 1} + \frac{me^{-\frac{2ikm\pi}{m-1}} - me^{-\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}}}{e^{-\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}} - 1} - \frac{me^{\frac{2ikm\pi}{m-1}} - e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}}}{e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}} - 1} \right] \quad (314)$$

$$+ \frac{(e^{\frac{2ikm\pi}{m-1}} - e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}})e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}}}{(e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}} - 1)^2} - \frac{me^{-\frac{2ikm\pi}{m-1}} - e^{-\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}}}{e^{-\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}} - 1} + \frac{(e^{-\frac{2ikm\pi}{m-1}} - e^{-\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}})e^{-\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}}}{(e^{-\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}} - 1)^2} \quad (315)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{-me^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}}}{e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}} - 1} + \frac{-me^{-\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}}}{e^{-\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}} - 1} + \frac{e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}}}{e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}} - 1} \right] \quad (316)$$

$$+ \frac{(e^{\frac{2ikm\pi}{m-1}} - e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}})e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}}}{(e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}} - 1)^2} + \frac{e^{-\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}}}{e^{-\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}} - 1} + \frac{(e^{-\frac{2ikm\pi}{m-1}} - e^{-\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}})e^{-\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}}}{(e^{-\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}} - 1)^2} \quad (317)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2(e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}} - 1)} \left[-me^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}} + e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}} + \frac{(e^{\frac{2ikm\pi}{m-1}} - e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}})e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}}}{e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}} - 1} \right] \quad (318)$$

$$+ \frac{1}{2(e^{-\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}} - 1)} \left[-me^{-\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}} + e^{-\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}} + \frac{(e^{-\frac{2ikm\pi}{m-1}} - e^{-\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}})e^{-\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}}}{e^{-\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}} - 1} \right]. \quad (319)$$

Now I use

$$\frac{1}{2(e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}} - 1)} = \frac{e^{-\frac{ik\pi}{m-1}}}{2(e^{\frac{ik\pi}{m-1}} - e^{-\frac{ik\pi}{m-1}})} = \frac{e^{-\frac{ik\pi}{m-1}}}{4i \sin(\frac{k\pi}{m-1})}, \quad (320)$$

$$\frac{1}{2(e^{-\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}} - 1)} = \frac{e^{\frac{ik\pi}{m-1}}}{2(e^{-\frac{ik\pi}{m-1}} - e^{\frac{ik\pi}{m-1}})} = -\frac{e^{\frac{ik\pi}{m-1}}}{2(e^{\frac{ik\pi}{m-1}} - e^{-\frac{ik\pi}{m-1}})} = -\frac{e^{\frac{ik\pi}{m-1}}}{4i \sin(\frac{k\pi}{m-1})}. \quad (321)$$

With that, the formulas are:

$$= \frac{e^{-\frac{ik\pi}{m-1}}}{4i \sin\left(\frac{k\pi}{m-1}\right)} \left[-me^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}} + e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}} + \frac{(e^{\frac{2ikm\pi}{m-1}} - e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}})e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}}e^{-\frac{ik\pi}{m-1}}}{2i \sin\left(\frac{k\pi}{m-1}\right)} \right] \quad (322)$$

$$- \frac{e^{\frac{ik\pi}{m-1}}}{4i \sin\left(\frac{k\pi}{m-1}\right)} \left[-me^{-\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}} + e^{-\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}} - \frac{(e^{-\frac{2ikm\pi}{m-1}} - e^{-\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}})e^{-\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}}e^{\frac{ik\pi}{m-1}}}{2i \sin\left(\frac{k\pi}{m-1}\right)} \right] \quad (323)$$

$$= \frac{1}{4i \sin\left(\frac{k\pi}{m-1}\right)} \left[-me^{\frac{ik\pi}{m-1}} + e^{\frac{ik\pi}{m-1}} + \frac{e^{\frac{2ikm\pi}{m-1}} - e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}}}{2i \sin\left(\frac{k\pi}{m-1}\right)} \right] \quad (324)$$

$$- \frac{1}{4i \sin\left(\frac{k\pi}{m-1}\right)} \left[-me^{-\frac{ik\pi}{m-1}} + e^{-\frac{ik\pi}{m-1}} - \frac{e^{-\frac{2ikm\pi}{m-1}} - e^{-\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}}}{2i \sin\left(\frac{k\pi}{m-1}\right)} \right] \quad (325)$$

$$= \frac{1}{4i \sin\left(\frac{k\pi}{m-1}\right)} \left[-m(e^{\frac{ik\pi}{m-1}} - e^{-\frac{ik\pi}{m-1}}) + (e^{\frac{ik\pi}{m-1}} - e^{-\frac{ik\pi}{m-1}}) + \frac{(e^{\frac{2ikm\pi}{m-1}} + e^{-\frac{2ikm\pi}{m-1}}) - (e^{\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}} + e^{-\frac{2ik\pi}{m-1}})}{2i \sin\left(\frac{k\pi}{m-1}\right)} \right] \quad (326)$$

$$= \frac{1}{4i \sin\left(\frac{k\pi}{m-1}\right)} \left[-2im \sin\left(\frac{k\pi}{m-1}\right) + 2i \sin\left(\frac{k\pi}{m-1}\right) + \frac{\cos\left(\frac{2km\pi}{m-1}\right) - \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{m-1}\right)}{2i \sin\left(\frac{k\pi}{m-1}\right)} \right] \quad (327)$$

$$= \frac{-m+1}{2} - \frac{\cos\left(\frac{2km\pi}{m-1}\right) - \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{m-1}\right)}{4 \sin^2\left(\frac{k\pi}{m-1}\right)}. \quad (328)$$

In the end, one has to use the trigonometric identity:

$$\cos(x) - \cos(y) = -2 \sin\left(\frac{x+y}{2}\right) \sin\left(\frac{x-y}{2}\right). \quad (329)$$

So that in this case:

$$\cos\left(\frac{2km\pi}{m-1}\right) - \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{m-1}\right) = -2 \sin\left(k\pi \frac{m+1}{m-1}\right) \sin\left(k\pi \frac{m-1}{m-1}\right) \quad (330)$$

$$= -2 \sin\left(k\pi \frac{m+1}{m-1}\right) \sin(k\pi) \quad (331)$$

$$= 0. \quad (332)$$

So that in the end one obtains

$$= \frac{-m+1}{2} - \frac{1}{4 \sin^2\left(\frac{k\pi}{m-1}\right)} \cdot 0 \quad (333)$$

$$= \frac{-m+1}{2} \quad (334)$$

$$= -\frac{m-1}{2}. \quad (335)$$

Leading to

$$\lambda_k = \frac{1}{m^2}, \forall k \neq m-1. \quad (336)$$

Which is exactly what I wanted to show.

A.10. Proof of the Non-Alignment of the Series-Coefficients

I want to shown for which $1 \leq k \leq m-1$ and $1 \leq l \leq M$

$$a_k - \lambda_l = 0. \quad (337)$$

We will see that M is not important in this calculation, which is important since it is not clear how the relation of M and $m-1$ is *a priori*.

$$a_k - \lambda_l = \frac{1}{m^4} \sum_{i,j=1}^{m-1} \sum_{n,\nu=1}^{m-1} \left[\cos\left(\frac{2\pi(t_i - t_j)(m-1)}{k(t_m - t_1)}\right) - \cos\left(\frac{2\pi(t_n - t_\nu)l}{(t_m - t_1)}\right) \right] \quad (338)$$

$$= \frac{1}{m^4} \sum_{i,j=1}^{m-1} \sum_{n,\nu=1}^{m-1} \left[-2 \sin\left(\frac{\pi(t_i - t_j)(m-1)}{k(t_m - t_1)} - \frac{\pi(t_n - t_\nu)l}{(t_m - t_1)}\right) \right] \quad (339)$$

$$\sin\left(\frac{\pi(t_i - t_j)(m-1)}{k(t_m - t_1)} + \frac{\pi(t_n - t_\nu)l}{(t_m - t_1)}\right)]. \quad (340)$$

Since the summation index in the two sums is arbitrary, since the addition is commutative, we can choose $n = i, \nu = j$, resulting in

$$a_k - \lambda_l = \frac{-2}{m^4} \sum_{i,j=1}^{m-1} \left[\sin\left(\frac{\pi(t_i - t_j)(m-1)}{k(t_m - t_1)} - \frac{\pi(t_i - t_j)l}{(t_m - t_1)}\right) \right] \quad (341)$$

$$\sin\left(\frac{\pi(t_i - t_j)(m-1)}{k(t_m - t_1)} + \frac{\pi(t_i - t_j)l}{(t_m - t_1)}\right)] \quad (342)$$

$$= \frac{-2}{m^4} \sum_{i,j=1}^{m-1} \left[\sin\left(\frac{\pi(t_i - t_j)}{t_m - t_1} \left(\frac{m-1}{k} - l\right)\right) \sin\left(\frac{\pi(t_i - t_j)}{t_m - t_1} \left(\frac{m-1}{k} + l\right)\right) \right]. \quad (343)$$

For this to be zero, there are two options. First, the terms are non-negative and add up to zero, or second, the individual terms are all zero. Since m, l, k are parameters that are not iterated throughout the summation, for the first option to be the case, some assumptions have to be made on the t_i, t_j , which violate generality. Therefore, we continue with option 2, which leads to the following equations. If one of these equalities holds, the entire sum is zero.

$$\frac{m-1}{k} - l = 0 \quad (344)$$

$$\frac{m-1}{k} + l = 0 \quad (345)$$

$$\frac{m-1}{k} - l = z \frac{t_m - t_1}{t_i - t_j} \quad \forall i \neq j \text{ and } z \in \mathbb{Z} \quad (346)$$

$$\frac{m-1}{k} + l = z \frac{t_m - t_1}{t_i - t_j} \quad \forall i \neq j \text{ and } z \in \mathbb{Z}. \quad (347)$$

Since the last two equations have to be true $\forall i \neq j$, it follows that $\frac{t_m - t_1}{t_i - t_j} \in \mathbb{Z}$ for all pairs of values, which is only the case of the simple periodic timeseries, so they can be omitted to

maintain generality.

One then finally obtains these two equations:

$$l = \frac{m-1}{k} \quad (348)$$

$$l = -\frac{m-1}{k}. \quad (349)$$

Since $l, k \in \mathbb{N}$ and therefore $l, k > 0$, this reduces to just one equation

$$l = \frac{m-1}{k}. \quad (350)$$

This has only two solutions for $l, k \in \mathbb{N}$: $k = 1$ resulting in $l = m - 1$ and $k = m - 1$ resulting in $l = 1$. All the other solutions would lead to $l \notin \mathbb{N}$, since for two natural numbers q, p with $1 \neq q \neq p \neq 1, q/p \in \mathbb{Q}$. Therefore

$$a_k - \lambda_l = 0 \text{ if and only if } (l = m - 1 \wedge k = 1) \vee (l = 1 \wedge k = m - 1). \quad (351)$$

Which is what I wanted to show.

B. Data Availability Statement

In Zenodo, at 10.5281/zenodo.17072119, are the codes which were used to create and calculate the analytical examples discussed above. They also feature a Python3 and a FORTRAN95 script, which contains the functions/subroutines to calculate the CCM, its ACF, the OM, its ACF and the PSE of them. It also features the AvIT-Expansion and the LANGE-Expansion. Furthermore, the code for the analysis of the Geysers data is given, with the subset of data the methods were tested.

The original geysers data from Eibl et al. can be found here: <https://doi.org/10.5880/GFZ.2.1.2019.005> [7].

C. Declaration of Independent Work

I hereby declare that I have produced this work independently within the framework of the supervision and without outside assistance, and have used only the sources and tools stated. I have clearly identified the sources of any sections from other works that I have quoted or given in essence. I declare that this work has not been submitted to any university or any examination authority in the current or any similar form. I am aware of the Richtlinie zur Sicherung guter wissenschaftlicher Praxis für Studierende an der Universität Potsdam (Plagiatsrichtlinie) - Vom 20. Oktober 2010".

Potsdam, September 16, 2025
(Lütje T.H. Lange)